

D5.1 Policy report on the characteristics of patients' mobility across Europe, the EU role and the possible gains from an increase in such mobility

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AUTHORS: Rosella Levaggi (RL), Markus Frischhut (MF)
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Abbreviations

Art.	Article
AT	Austria
C/E	cost effectiveness (ratio)
CAR	chimeric antigen receptor (CAR-T cell therapy)
cf.	confer (= compare)
CIFREL	Inter-University Research Centre on Local and Regional Finance
COM	(European) Commission document
CPMS	Clinical Patient Management System
CZ	Czechia
DE	Germany
DoA	Description of the action
ECJ	European Court of Justice
EEA	European Economic Area
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EHIC	European Health Insurance Card
ERN	European Reference Networks
et al.	et alii (= and others)
etc.	et cetera (=and other things)
EU	European Union
FLASH	Flexible Approaches to Support Health through financing
GA	Grant agreement
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
HLY	healthy life years
HTA	Health Technology Assessment
i.e.	id est (= that is)
ibid.	ibidem (= in the same place)
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
FLASH – Flexible Approaches to Support Health through financing	

IT	Information Technology
lit	litera (= letter)
MS	Member State(s)
MSA	Member State of Affiliation
MST	Member State of Treatment
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OJ	Official Journal (of the EU)
p	page
para	paragraph
PD	portable document
PMD	Directive 2011/24/EU on the application of patients' rights in cross-border healthcare
pp	pages
PPP	purchasing power parity
S1	form for full healthcare under Articles 17 and 18 SSCR
S2	form for planned care under Article 20 SSCR
SK	Slovakia
SSC-IR	Regulation (EC) No 987/2009 laying down the procedure for implementing the SSCR
SSCR	Regulation (EC) No 883/2004 on the coordination of social security systems
SWD	Staff Working Document
TFEU	Treaty on the Functioning of the European
U.S.	United States
UK	United Kingdom
WP	Work package

Glossary of terms

Please note, the following terms are partially based on the official definitions as provided in the relevant EU legal documents, respectively partially on SWD(2022) 200 final 12.5.2022.

Border region patient mobility: patients moving between two neighbouring Member States (MS)¹, in order to seek or receive healthcare in close vicinity (not exactly defined) between the place of residence and the place of treatment

Cross-border healthcare: healthcare provided (or medicines prescribed) in a MS other than the Member State of affiliation (MSA, see below); applies to the 27 EU MS, as well as to the European Economic Area (EEA)/European Free Trade Association (EFTA) countries of Norway, Iceland and Liechtenstein, and in case of the SSCR (and the SSC-IR; see below) also to Switzerland and the United Kingdom (UK; under the Brexit rules)

Effectiveness: a treatment, a procedure, a payment system, which is able to reach the objective for which it has been devised

Efficiency: the ability of a treatment/procedure/payment to reach a specific objective at the lowest possible cost

Equity: the ability of a treatment/procedure/payment system to redistribute benefit across patients' groups or at least to avoid that only some groups may benefit from its implementation

EU patient mobility directive (PMD): Directive 2011/24/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2011 on the application of patients' rights in cross-border healthcare

EU social security coordination regulation (SSCR): Regulation (EC) No 883/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on the coordination of social security systems

EU social security coordination implementing regulation (SSC-IR): Regulation (EC) No 987/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 September

¹ While border-region patient mobility could also take place between an EU MS and a third country, for this report we completely exclude this situation.

2009 laying down the procedure for implementing Regulation (EC) No 883/2004 on the coordination of social security systems

European Health Insurance Card (EHIC): card issued by the competent institution (e.g. national health insurance), which enables patients to receive medically necessary, state-mandated healthcare during a temporary stay in another MS or EEA/EFTA country, Switzerland or the UK (under the Brexit rules); treatment is provided under the same conditions and at the same cost as the persons insured in the MST (see below)

European Reference Networks (ERN): “virtual networks involving healthcare providers across Europe”; they “aim to facilitate discussion on complex or rare diseases and conditions that require highly specialised treatment, and concentrated knowledge and resources”²

Flexibility: the quality of bending easily without breaking; the ability to be easily modified; the willingness to change or compromise (Stevenson, 2010, p669)

Full healthcare (according to the SSCR): for persons who reside in a MS other than the competent MSA (e.g. for posted workers, cross-border workers, pensioners) and asked for a certificate (portable document S1) that establishes a right to full healthcare coverage in the MS of residence (Article 17 SSCR) and also in the MSA (according to Article 18 SSCR)

Healthcare: means health services provided by health professionals to patients to assess maintain or restore their state of health, including the prescription, dispensation and provision of medicinal products and medical devices

Member State of affiliation (MSA): Member State that is competent to grant to the insured person a prior authorisation under EU social security law (especially SSCR and SSC-IR) and to subsequently cover the costs

Member State of treatment (MST): Member State on whose territory healthcare is actually provided to the patient (in case of telemedicine, this is the Member State where the provider is established); can also be Norway, Iceland or Liechtenstein, and in case of the EU social security law also Switzerland and the United Kingdom (under the Brexit rules)

Multi-level systems: an organisation (usually public), who's decision chain is set at a different level; the organisation may be more hierarchical (the higher level

² Cf. https://ec.europa.eu/health/european-reference-networks/overview_en.

delegates the implementation of a specific decision to lower levels) or more decentralised (the higher-level delegates function to lower tiers and coordinate their actions)

Patient mobility: cross-border healthcare (provided or prescribed outside the MSA) where the patient actually moves (or is being moved) to the MST (or EEA/EFTA countries); hence, excluding situations where health professionals or only the service (e.g. telemedicine) are crossing the border

Patient: human being seeking or receiving healthcare

Planned healthcare (according to the PMD): healthcare provided or medicines prescribed in a country (including EEA/EFTA countries) other than the MSA based on the PMD, can require prior authorisation (according to Article 8 PMD)

Planned healthcare (according to the SSCR): situation of an insured person travelling to another MS (or EEA/EFTA country, Switzerland or the UK [UK; under the Brexit rules]) with the purpose of receiving benefits in kind during the stay; necessity to seek prior authorisation from the competent institution (according to Article 20 SSCR; S2 form)

Prior authorisation: authorisation that patients need to receive from their competent institution (e.g. national health insurance institution) before seeking cross-border healthcare and often a precondition for subsequent reimbursement

Resilience: “the ability to face economic, social and environmental shocks or persistent structural changes in a fair, sustainable and inclusive way”³

Unplanned – or necessary – health care: healthcare (including emergency care) received in an EU MS, an EEA/EFTA country, Switzerland or the UK (under the Brexit rules), which becomes ‘necessary on medical grounds’ during a ‘temporary stay’ (for work, study, or leisure) and without the initial intention of the patient to travel to receive treatment in this MST; based on EU social security law (Article 19 SSCR, SSC-IR; EHIC), or in a private clinic based on the PMD

³ Regulation (EU) 2021/241 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 February 2021 establishing the Recovery and Resilience Facility, OJ 2021 L 57/17, Art. 2 para 5.
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Executive summary

Healthcare provision remains a national competence in line with the vertical distribution of competences, but there are several areas where EU intervention may improve welfare. One of this area is certainly health care, a sector where the EU is rather active. The aim of this report is to examine the state-of-the-art as concerns patients' mobility and to suggest some areas, where the EU may be more proactive to improve patients' experience.

The review of the data on patients' mobility shows that care is often received in a neighbouring country. This choice could derive from a perceived **quality** difference in the care provided, but the pattern of mobility suggests that there might be other drivers such as **proximity** and health care **availability**. At present, there does not appear to be uniformity across Member States in dealing with mobility. Apart from S1 mobility and unplanned care, Member States (and patients) seem to use both mobility under social security coordination (S2) and the patient mobility directive sometimes for the same treatment, even though the financial implications and the legal requirements are different. In some areas, where bilateral agreements do not exist, the health care cost difference (which may reflect quality differences but also cost difference due to the input prices) may be a hurdle to mobility.

We suggest that the EU may have a primary role in at least four different areas: the treatment of **rare diseases** and state-of-the-art protocols to share innovative treatments, an area where the EU is already active with initiative to develop networks and specific investments into financing research. In **border regions**, because of the geographical location of patients and health care services, it may be more appropriate and cost effective to treat patients in neighbouring countries. This activity could benefit from EU intervention, for example, as concerns establishing some rules for setting reimbursement prices when national costs are quite different and when this difference is mainly driven by inputs. The same is true for **patient driven mobility**, which derives from the autonomous choice of the patient to be treated abroad and new initiatives that may allow to **better use spare capacity** across European countries. In this respect, it is interesting to note that the EU may also play a role in reducing the need to receive health care abroad. With the advent of **e-health technologies** for some diseases, the patient will be able to receive the state-of-the-art care in her own country, without the need to move. An interesting development is the establishment of virtual consultation panels through the Clinical Patient Management System (CPMS), a dedicated IT platform and telemedicine tool developed by the Commission to allow healthcare providers from all over the EU to work together virtually to diagnose and treat patients.

From a legal perspective, one way of achieving a more **solidarity**-based approach would be to revise the existing cross-border healthcare regime. For example, merging the directive into the regulation would reduce complexity, allow for a general (solidarity-based) revision, and thereby might reduce injustice related to knowledge (epistemic injustice in a broad sense).

1. Introduction

1.1. Point of departure and structure

The FLASH project, 'Flexible Approaches to Support Health through **financing**', focusses, amongst others, on the key issues to design an effective health care system pandemic. One key learning is the importance of **flexibility** in funding and organization of health systems, as there are several challenges for **health care systems** that require efficient and flexible financing mechanisms to be successfully addressed. One of the aims of the FLASH project is to provide evidence on the ability of existing financing mechanisms and contracts to address such challenges and study **new solutions** to achieve more **effective, efficient and equitable** health care systems.

In this context, work package (WP) 5 is dedicated studying patient mobility in multi-level systems, with a special emphasis on **resilience**. This report focusses on the **characteristics of patients' mobility** across the European Union (EU) and beyond, the **EU's role** and the possible gains from an **increase** in such mobility.

Although cross-border patient mobility affects a minor share of the population, it has **potentials** to increase the effectiveness and the resilience of health care systems, which have not been fully explored so far. Patients usually opt to travel if care is **not available** in their home country, but for the population living in **border regions** cross-border care is simply more accessible due to travel distance. In addition, restructuring plans at national level to increase efficiency in the hospital sector result in integration of care (OECD/European Union 2020) may have created health care deserts in some border areas. Inhabitants and visitors of border areas thus often suffer from significantly worsened accessibility to healthcare providers than the inland population. Additionally, when two neighbouring countries have different price levels, healthcare workforce from the poorer country commutes cross-border for higher wages. Brain drain leaves the poorer country's border area with insufficient number of doctors and nurses. The EU law which allows labour to freely travel, but forbids patients to freely travel cross-border for care significantly threatens safety of border areas, particularly in these specific cases.⁴ Thus, cross-border mobility in these cases is not a choice, but a matter of safety.

Cross-border healthcare can be clustered in a binary way in unplanned and planned healthcare. This policy report will mainly focus on **planned** care (and its different reimbursement models), while also covering some questions of unplanned (i.e. necessary) care.

⁴ Examples include CZ-DE, CZ-AT, SK-AT, etc.

Chapter 2 depicts the **status quo** in terms of the legal framework and the division of competences between the supra-national EU and the Member States (MS). Which questions can be regulated by the EU? Who is in charge for basic questions of health care systems?

Based on this, Chapter 3 will depict the **mobility flows** that take place based on this legal framework (cf. Grant Agreement, Description of the action [DoA], p. 13). Chapter 4 sheds more light on the **reasons** for mobility, taking a closer look at EU **reference networks** (Chapter 4.1), patient mobility in **border regions** (Chapter 4.2) and **patients driven** mobility (Chapter 4.3).

WP5 “aims at designing a system for patients’ mobility to improve quality of care across Member States and to reduce the quality gap among countries” (DoA, p. 13). Therefore, Chapter 5 will focus on some legal questions of **quality** of care, addressing the question which MS is in charge of quality of care and which other legal prerequisites can be derived from EU law and the case-law of the European Court of Justice (ECJ).

Chapter 6 will provide both a **summary** of the key findings and also provide an **outlook** to the questions, in the view to propose new systems to govern patients’ mobility flows across the EU.

1.2. Key characteristics of patient mobility

Health care systems rely on geographical boundaries that are necessary to secure financial stability and to ensure adequate **planning** of health care infrastructure and capacity.⁵ However, the creation of an enlarged EU has created some important challenges to this model. In fact, EU enlargement has meant an increase in cross-country **disparities** concerning the following aspects: income, life expectancy, efficiency in public spending and in available technologies (see Annex 1 for more information).

These differences and the enlargement of the number of countries in the EU have spurred the debate on the **role** that the **EU** should have in health care provisions (Guthmuller, Paruolo, and Verzillo 2021). While the literature shows that health care provision is better left at national level, the EU may clearly play a more proactive role in the provision of some functions such as procurement and incentives to innovation (CIFREL 2020).⁶

⁵ On planning requirements, see also below at note 114.

⁶ On the legal framework (and the EU’s role), see Chapter 2.

Some authors recognise that the **EU** may probably not be a health care provider or the regulator of the system (given the heterogeneity that exists as both concerns health care finance and health care delivery and organisation). However, literature seems to agree that the EU may play a prominent role in this sector as both concerns **equity** and **efficiency** on specific interventions such as prevention or procurement. The recent Covid-19 crisis has shown that several other function can be better organised at EU level. For example, the **collaboration** among research centres can be enhanced by EU **funding** and in this the programmes put forth by the EU are rather effective (Schmidt et al. 2022; Bobek et al. 2018; Guthmuller, Paruolo, and Verzillo 2021). However, the Covid-19 crisis has also shown that the EU may play a role as a supra-national purchaser for goods and services (i.e. **'joint procurement'**). Hence, it may allow MS to have better deals in the bargaining with the industry and it may also have an important role in planning spare capacity to face unexpected crises (Buso et al. 2023; Pircher 2022).

At present, one of the sectors in which the EU is more active is certainly cross border patient mobility, by which we understand the fact that patients move between MS to seek or receive healthcare. Based on EU law that has strengthened **patients' rights** to seek medical treatment in other MS, patients' mobility has been steadily rising until 2016 (Mullan, Wilson, and Guillermo-Ramirez 2022; Olsson, De Smedth Lynn, and De Wispelaere Fredric 2021; Peralta-Santos and Perelman 2018), even though it is still a **marginal phenomenon**, which was obviously also affected by the Covid-19 pandemic. For example, the same is not true for America, where medical tourism is becoming a rather standard practice (Dalen and Alpert 2019). The **globalization** is deemed to increase the demand and need for patient mobility and its governance should be an important priority at EU level.

In the EU, the patient mobility directive (**PMD**)⁷ was introduced in 2011 with the following aims: "to establish rules for facilitating access to safe and high-quality cross-border healthcare in the Union and to ensure patient mobility in accordance with the principles established by the Court of Justice and to promote cooperation on healthcare between Member States, whilst fully respecting the responsibilities of the Member States for the definition of social security benefits relating to health and for the organisation and delivery of healthcare and medical care and social security benefits, in particular for sickness"⁸. At the same time, the objective was not to encourage patients to receive treatment outside their MSA.⁹ Patient mobility can be seen as falling within the passive (i.e. the receiver of the service crosses the

⁷ Directive 2011/24/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2011 on the application of patients' rights in cross-border healthcare, OJ 2011 L 88/45.

⁸ Recital 10 PMD.

⁹ Recital 4 PMD.

border) freedom of services (Art. 56 TFEU¹⁰) and can be restricted in case of the proportional application of accepted reasons of justification. As the aim of the PMD was to “establish rules for facilitating access to safe and high-quality cross-border healthcare in the Union”,¹¹ one can conclude that the PMD was aiming at qualitative, but not quantitative increases. Besides the PMD (linked to the freedom to receive services), the EU has long-standing rules on **social security coordination**¹², linked to the free movement of workers.

In this policy report, we will argue that this objective may be reached by **regulating and promoting patient mobility** across Europe. Patient mobility may be a driver for equity and efficiency at European level in several different areas. This includes the treatment of **rare diseases** and state-of-the-art protocols to share **innovative treatments**, as well as cross border mobility in **border regions**. In border regions, because of the geographical location of patients and health care services, it may be more appropriate and cost effective to treat patients in neighbouring countries. This also includes patient driven mobility, which derives from the autonomous choice of the patient to be treated abroad and new initiatives that may allow better using spare capacity across European Countries. The Covid-19 pandemic had made it necessary to use innovative models to share resources at EU level and we argue that it may well be possible to use some of these instruments in a more systematic way in order to improve efficiency and equity in health care provision.

2. Legal framework

2.1. The constitutional framework (Art. 168 TFEU, etc.)

The EU role in the context of cross-border healthcare has to take place within the constitutional framework, which for health can be found primarily¹³ in Art. 168 TFEU. This article can be described as following a principle and exceptions approach. The **principle** is that when acting in this context, the EU has to respect “the responsibilities of the Member States for the definition of their health policy and for the organisation and delivery of health services and medical care”, which includes the “management of health services and medical care and the allocation of the resources assigned to them”.¹⁴ The MS responsibility for the organisation and the allocation of resources clearly also comprises the question of financing of health systems.

¹⁰ Consolidated version: OJ 2016 C 202/47.

¹¹ Recital 10 PMD.

¹² See below, Chapter 2.2.

¹³ On other provisions of EU primary law, see below.

¹⁴ Art. 168 para 7 TFEU.

The **exceptions** to this principle do not concern this key competence of each MS to decide on the organisation and financing of each health system, but rather the way a MS exercises this responsibility. There are two perspectives, how EU law can influence this basic MS competence.

First via **individual patients** relying on the already mentioned passive **freedom of services** (Art. 56 TFEU), i.e. the subjective right to seek the same treatment (as in the MSA) in another EU MS and to be reimbursed up to the same level (not exceeding the amount of the actual costs). The corresponding ECJ case-law has been codified in the PMD. Besides the fundamental freedom to receive services, also mobile workers enjoy several entitlements under the **free movement of workers** under EU social security law (see below).

The **second** impact is not via the EU entitling individual patients, but via the **EU institutions harmonizing** national law, where Art. 168 TFEU allows for such legislative activities. While Art. 168 para 5 TFEU specifically excludes harmonization in the context of serious cross-border threats to health, the EU can actually adopt EU secondary law in order to meet common safety concerns (Art. 168 para 4 TFEU). This competence covers organs and substances of human origin, blood and blood derivatives (lit a), the veterinary and phytosanitary field (lit b), as well as in case of medicinal products (or pharmaceuticals) and medical devices (lit c). Besides that, the EU has also had quite some influence based on other provisions of the TFEU, especially Art. 114 on harmonization in the internal market.¹⁵

In conclusion, the MS have the power to take basic decisions of how to organise (centralised, or decentralised) and how to finance (Bismarck vs. Beveridge) their health system, as well as to decide who should have public health insurance and under which conditions. However, in exercising this power, they have to respect the principle of non-discrimination based on nationality (as individuals have a subjective right that they can enforce before national courts), and they have to respect all the EU law that has been enacted based on Art. 168 TFEU, but also other (non-health) provisions of this EU constitutional framework, defining the EU's role in this context.

2.2. Different scenarios

Cross-border healthcare can first be differentiated in **planned** vs. **unplanned** (especially, necessary) treatment (see Table 1 below).

Unplanned treatment covers healthcare that becomes necessary on medical grounds during a temporary stay in another Member State according to EU **social**

¹⁵ For a good overview, see Hervey (2023).

security law. EU law provides for rules (only) on the **coordination**, however not for the harmonization, of social security systems. These rules can be found in EU Regulation social security coordination (SSCR)¹⁶ and the corresponding implementing regulation (SSC-IR)¹⁷. In a similar way as the PMD, both social security regulations also apply to the EEA¹⁸. However, unlike the PMD, these two social security regulations also apply in relation to Switzerland¹⁹.

- However, as will be depicted below, this category of unplanned healthcare regulated in **Article 19** SSCR is broader (i.e., '**necessary care**') than just 'emergency care' and these rights are embodied in the European Health Insurance Card (**EHIC**). This card issued by the competent institution (e.g. national health insurance) enables patients to receive medically necessary, state-mandated healthcare during a temporary stay in another MS or EEA/EFTA country, Switzerland or the UK. Treatment is provided under the same conditions and at the same cost as the persons insured in the MST. For further details, see below Chapter 2.2.1.
- Unplanned care is also regulated in **Articles 17 and 18** SSCR ('**full healthcare coverage**'). In this category a person that resides in a MS other than the competent MSA (e.g. posted workers, cross-border workers, pensioners) can ask for a certificate (portable document **S1**) that establishes a right to full healthcare coverage in both the MS of residence (Article 17 SSCR) and also in the MSA (Article 18 SSCR). For further details, see below Chapter 2.2.2.

Planned care originally only took place under the SSCR until in the *Kohll*²⁰ case the ECJ has also enabled planned cross-border healthcare under the freedom of services (Art. 56 TFEU), now codified in the PMD. Hence, patients nowadays enjoy two²¹ possibilities so seek planned treatment abroad.

¹⁶ Regulation (EC) No 883/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on the coordination of social security systems, OJ 2004 L 166/1, as amended by OJ 2019 L 186/21.

¹⁷ Regulation (EC) No 987/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 September 2009 laying down the procedure for implementing Regulation (EC) No 883/2004 on the coordination of social security systems, OJ 2009 L 284/1, as amended by OJ 2017 L 76/13.

¹⁸ I.e., likewise, to the EEA/EFTA countries of Norway, Iceland and Liechtenstein.

¹⁹ In the following, this report will not focus on the UK (see glossary). For further details, see (Bieback, 2022), pp. 251–287.

²⁰ Case C-158/96 *Kohll v Union des caisses de maladie* ECLI:EU:C:1998:171.

²¹ Theoretically, patients could also still rely on Art. 56 TFEU, but the ECJ seems to prefer a interpret Art. 56 TFEU and the PMD in a uniform way.

Table 1 - Planned vs. unplanned care in EU law

	Unplanned care		Planned care	
	Residence ²² in MST (e.g. posted workers)	Temporary stay ²³ in MST (e.g. tourist)	Trip to MST in order to get treatment	
Main legal basis/es	Art. 17, 18 SSCR	Art. 19 SSCR	Art. 20 SSCR	Art. 56 TFEU (incl. ECJ case-law) and PMD
Key characteristics	Full healthcare coverage in the MS of residence (Art. 17 SSCR) for persons who reside in MS other than MSA, as well as in MSA (Art. 18 SSCR)	Treatment ' necessary on medical grounds' during a 'temporary stay' (work, study, or leisure) and without initial intention to travel to receive treatment in MST ('emergency care') ²⁴	Insured person travelling to MST with the purpose (i.e. planned SSCR) of receiving benefits in kind during the stay	Insured person travelling to MST with the purpose (i.e. planned PMD) of receiving benefits in kind (or medicines prescribed) during the stay
Countries covered	EU 27 and EEA/EFTA, plus Switzerland, UK			EU 27 and EEA/EFTA
Prior authorization (p.a.)	No p.a., just S1 form (Art. 17)	No p.a., just EHIC	Yes, p.a. and S2 form	Yes, p.a. especially for hospital treatment (cf. Art. 8 PMD) ²⁵

²² According to Art. 1 lit. j SSCR, 'residence' "means the place where a person habitually resides".

²³ According to Art. 1 lit. k SSCR, 'stay' "means temporary residence".

²⁴ In case of receiving the treatment in a private clinic, the patient can rely on the PMD.

²⁵ Different MS have different ways, how prior authorization can be requested under the PMD; see Olsson et al. (2023), p. 46.

- First, under the rules provided nowadays in **Article 20 SSCR**. The SSCR is linked to the free movement of workers that also requires coordination of social security rules. This concerns the rights of an insured person travelling to another country with the purpose of receiving benefits in kind during the stay apply to the 27 EU-MS, the EEA/EFTA countries, Switzerland and the UK (under the Brexit rules). Art. 20 SSCR always requires prior authorization, embodied in the **S2 form**. For further details, see below Chapter 2.2.3.
- Second, the case-law of the ECJ based on the freedom to receive services (Art. 56 TFEU) has been codified in the **PMD**. This directive, which needs to be implemented into national law, sometimes requires prior authorization, but not under all circumstance. The rights of patients seeking healthcare provided (or medicines prescribed) apply to the 27 EU-MS as well as the EEA/EFTA countries, but not to Switzerland or the UK. For further details, see below Chapter 2.2.4.

2.2.1 Necessary treatment under Art. 19 SSCR

According to **Art. 19 SSCR**, insured persons (as well as family members) staying outside the MSA “shall be entitled to the benefits in kind which become necessary on medical grounds during their stay, taking into account the nature of the benefits and the expected length of the stay”. This person then will receive benefits like other people having health insurance from the MST.

While in theory the wording – “become necessary on medical grounds during their stay” – shall allow for a clear **distinction** to be drawn between unplanned care, as opposed to planned treatment, this distinction can nonetheless prove tricky. In EU social security law, the concept of ‘necessary’ care has replaced the previous concept of ‘immediate’ care.²⁶ First, it is important for the insured persons (workers, self-employed persons, students, pensioners, etc.) covered to clarify a ‘**temporary stay**’, which can be defined in a negative way as opposing it to the concept of ‘residence’ (i.e., the place where a person habitually resides).²⁷ Second, similar to ECJ case *Watts*²⁸, this assessment of whether the treatment is ‘**necessary**’ has to be

²⁶ European Commission (2011), p. 1. See also, for further details, Decision No S3 of 12 June 2009 defining the benefits covered by Articles 19(1) and 27(1) of Regulation (EC) No 883/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Article 25(A)(3) of Regulation (EC) No 987/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council, OJ 2010 C 106/40.

²⁷ European Commission (2011), p. 2; relevant facts to assess a person’s ‘centre of interests’ are a “person’s intention, his family status and family ties, the source of his/her income, the nature of his/her activities, etc”. Hence, an Erasmus student or a posted worker can still fall within the concept of a ‘temporary stay’. See also Article 11 of Regulation (EC) No 987/2009 (note 17).

²⁸ Case C-372/04 *Watts* ECLI:EU:C:2006:325, paras 68-79; see also at note 64.

done by a **medical** doctor based on medical, not administrative criteria.²⁹ The ECJ has clarified that in this context of 'unplanned care', the requirement of 'necessary care' cannot be interpreted as a "requirement that the illness which necessitated the treatment in question manifested itself suddenly [!] during that stay, making that treatment immediately [!] necessary"³⁰. This has to be seen against the background of the **purpose** of the concept of 'necessary care', which is "to enable a person to continue his/her stay under safe medical conditions"³¹. Linked to the **length of stay**, a tourist staying for two weeks is entitled to an operation after having broken her leg, whereas a student staying for half a year would in addition also be entitled to physiotherapy.³² As stated by Art. 25 para 3 SSC-IR, an insured person shall not be forced to return home. In a negative sense, it can be concluded that this concept normally excludes preventive care, such as vaccinations.³³ In case of persons suffering from **existing or chronic diseases**, 'necessary care' does not only concern treatments that "became suddenly necessary during the stay abroad", but also includes "the continuation of treatment that started in the State of residence but that needs to be continued", such as regularly dialysis or monthly chemotherapy.³⁴ In case of **pregnancy and childbirth**, 'necessary care' has to be understood as including the related healthcare, "except when the sole purpose of the stay is to give birth, e.g. in border regions".³⁵

Another tricky situation refers to a person that, for example, **breaks their leg** in Czechia and then crosses the border to get treatment in Austria, maybe because the nearest hospital is closer on the other side of the border. The **time of occurrence of pain** can be relevant here. If the pain first occurs in Austria, treatment may be qualified as 'necessary'. On the other hand, if the pain already occurred in Czechia (i.e. before crossing the border), this could be qualified as planned care, unless it can be proven that there are reasons for which treatment cannot be postponed. The latter situation can occur in case of an expensive trip booked in advance, an important business appointment, etc.³⁶ As mentioned

²⁹ (European Commission 2011), p. 1.

³⁰ Case C-326/00 *IKA* ECLI:EU:C:2003:101, para 43.

³¹ European Commission (2011), p. 1.

³² European Commission (2011), p. 2.

³³ European Commission (2011), p. 2 unless if vaccinations become necessary to protect public health.

³⁴ European Commission (2011), p. 4. While for such type of treatment that is only available in specialised medical units there is no prior authorisation requirement, it is, nonetheless, recommended to contact the institution providing the care in the MST, to ensure the actual availability. For further examples (of the non-exhaustive list), see the Annex in OJ 2010 C 106/40 (referring to "prior agreement", but not 'prior authorisation').

³⁵ European Commission (2011), p. 3. However, this assessment has to be done on a case-by-case basis. For example, the situation of a migrant woman that wishes to give birth where she has the support of her family would be considered 'necessary care'.

³⁶ See (Bieback 2022) p. 274.

above, the assessment of whether the treatment is ‘necessary’ has to be done by a medical doctor, based on medical, not administrative criteria. Treatment that goes beyond what would be qualified as ‘necessary’ treatment would have to be covered under the rules for planned treatment (see below Chapters 2.2.3 and 2.2.4). The right is evidenced by the **EHIC**.

2.2.2 Full coverage under Articles 17 and 18 SSCR

According to **Art. 17 SSCR**, an insured person and family members who reside (hence, posted workers, cross-border workers) in a Member State other than the competent Member State, are entitled to receive in the Member State of residence benefits in kind. The latter are provided on behalf of the competent institution (i.e. in the end the MSA has to pay), by the institution of the place of residence (i.e. the MST), in accordance with the provisions of the legislation it applies, as though they were insured under the said legislation. Hence, so to say, they are integrated into the system of the MS of residence (the MST). You could also say that a fiction is created whereby the person is treated as if that person were insured in the MST. This could be beneficial (more rights in the MST compared to the MSA) or not (more rights in the MSA than in the MST).³⁷ The right is evidenced by the **portable document S1**³⁸.

In addition to Art. 17 SSCR, according to **Art. 18 SSCR**, the insured person and the members of his/her family residing in another MS shall **also** be entitled to benefits in kind while staying **back home** in the competent Member State (i.e. the **MSA**). According to this provision, the benefits in kind shall be provided by the competent institution and at its own expense (i.e. MST = MSA), in accordance with the provisions of the legislation it applies, as though the persons concerned resided in that Member State. This double (acc. to Art. 17 SSCR in the MS of residence and acc. to Art. 18 SSCR back home in the MSA) right to get treatment can be especially important for ‘frontier workers’³⁹. A **specific document is not necessary**,⁴⁰ as the person is insured and receives treatment in the MSA (only the residence is in another MS).

³⁷ See, for further details, Bieback (2022) p. 295.

³⁸ However, this only has a declaratory effect. Case C-178/97 *Banks and Others* ECLI:EU:C:2000:169, para 53. According to Art. 24 para 1 SSC-IR, the insured person and/or members of his family shall be obliged to register with the institution of the place of residence; their right to benefits in kind in the Member State of residence shall be certified by a document issued by the competent institution upon request of the insured person or upon request of the institution of the place of residence.

³⁹ According to Art. 1 lit. f SSCR, ‘frontier worker’ “means any person pursuing an activity as an employed or self-employed person in a Member State and who resides in another Member State to which he/she returns as a rule daily or at least once a week”.

⁴⁰ Cf. Bieback (2022), p. 301.

2.2.3 Planned healthcare under Art. 20 SSCR

After unplanned care, let us turn to planned treatment. The rules on **planned** treatment can be found in **Art. 20 SSCR**,⁴¹ entitled ‘travel with the purpose of receiving benefits in kind’. Hence, the decision to seek healthcare in another MS is taken before the crossing of the border. According to the ECJ a ‘planned treatment’ in another MS⁴² is based “on his own initiative”, in case the person argues that “treatment or treatment with the same efficacy was unavailable in his Member State of residence within a time limit which is medically justifiable”.⁴³ However, based on what has been mentioned above in case of ‘necessary’ (including ‘emergency’) care, this concept (**‘own initiative’**) should be seen as a negative description of ‘necessary’ (including ‘emergency’) care.

In this case, an insured person⁴⁴, basically, **always** has to ask for **prior authorisation**. As already mentioned, a MS can ask for prior authorization, but is **not obliged** to do so. According to Art. 20 para 2, there are **two requirements**: First, the “authorisation shall be accorded where the treatment in question is among the benefits provided for by the legislation in the Member State where the person concerned resides”. The second precondition refers to the question, if the person “cannot be given such treatment within a time limit which is medically justifiable, taking into account his/her current state of health and the probable course of his/her illness”.

It is for the MSA to define the **‘basket of care’**. Via EU law, the MSA “cannot, in principle, [be obliged] to extend such lists of medical benefits”.⁴⁵ Member States are free “to establish exhaustive lists of the medical benefits reimbursed” and are also “entitled to list precisely treatments or treatment methods or to state more generally the categories or types of treatments or treatment methods”.⁴⁶ The **S2 form** evidences this right to planned care under Art. 20 SSCR.⁴⁷

2.2.4 Planned healthcare under the PMD and related topics

Planned treatment can also⁴⁸ be sought under the **PMD**⁴⁹, which requires an overview (see Table 2) of these two EU documents, PMD and SSCR (Art. 20), allowing

⁴¹ For pensioners, see Art. 28 SSCR.

⁴² I.e., healthcare received in a Member State other than the State in which the insured person resides.

⁴³ Case C-777/18 *Vas Megyei Kormányhivatal (Cross-border healthcare)* ECLI:EU:C:2020:745, para 44.

⁴⁴ The same applies to family members (Art. 20 para 3 SSCR).

⁴⁵ Case C-173/09 *Elchinov* ECLI:EU:C:2010:581, para 58.

⁴⁶ Case C-173/09 *Elchinov* ECLI:EU:C:2010:581, paras 58 and 59.

⁴⁷ Cf. Art. 26 SSC-IR.

⁴⁸ While patients have a choice, the possibilities offered by the two scenarios cannot be used simultaneously; cf. also Olsson et al. (2023), p. 17.

⁴⁹ Different MS have different ways, how prior authorization can be requested under the PMD; see Olsson et al. (2023), p. 46.

for planned treatment in another MS (respectively Norway, Iceland or Liechtenstein).⁵⁰

Table 2 – Planned treatment abroad according to the SSCR and the PMD

	SSCR	PMD
Necessity of up-front payment	No up-front payment	Up-front payment
Reimbursement rates	MST ⁵¹ ; hence, same as for 'locals'	MSA; however, principle of non-discrimination to be observed
Health insurance	'Public health' insurance only	'Public health' insurance only
Healthcare providers	'Public' providers only	'Private' and 'public' providers

In either case, only **public health insurance**⁵² is covered, or in other words, if someone in addition has private health insurance, then treatment abroad takes place according to this individual contract under private law. Under the SSCR the idea is that someone who is entitled is treated in another MS in the same way as locally insured people. That is why under the SSCR the **rules** (of reimbursement) of the **MST apply**. Under the PMD the idea was not to burden the health budget of the MSA, hence a person can only seek abroad the same treatment and up until the same expenses, as at home. Hence, the rules of the **MSA** apply (and are exported in a certain sense). In terms of the **providers** where treatment can be sought abroad in case of the SSCR, these are **only 'public** providers⁵³, e.g., a public hospital, but only a contracted private general practitioner. In other words, providers that do not have a contract with the health insurance fund are not seen as 'public providers' in this context. As just mentioned, in case of the PMD the main concerns were of a budgetary nature, that is why the ECJ in a Greek case has **also** accepted if a patient has sought treatment in a **private** establishment abroad.⁵⁴

⁵⁰ Briefly, to note that unplanned treatment (normally SSCR) provided by a private provider (not covered by the SSCR) can be sought under the PMD; cf. also Olsson et al. (2023), p. 35.

⁵¹ The payment process takes places between the institutions of the MSA and the MST. If the patient has paid the cost of the treatment herself, "she can request reimbursement either in the country of treatment or when returning home"; SWD (2022) 200 final p. 110.

⁵² According to Art. 1 lit. c SSCR, 'insured person', "means any person satisfying the conditions required under the legislation of the Member State competent under Title II to have the right to benefits, taking into account the provisions of this Regulation".

⁵³ According to Art. 1 lit. va (i) SSCR, 'benefits in kind' means "benefits in kind provided for under the legislation [...] of a Member State which are intended to supply, make available, pay directly or reimburse the cost of medical care and products and services ancillary to that care".

⁵⁴ I.e. a Greek patient that was treated in the private London Bridge Hospital; Case C-444/05 *Stamatelaki* ECLI:EU:C:2007:231, paras 9 and 38.

This case-law has been codified in the PMD; hence, also there, both private and public providers are covered.⁵⁵

In practical terms, **prior authorisation** for planned healthcare has to be granted by the public health insurance. Prior authorisation can **basically**⁵⁶ be required under the **SSCR** (granted via the **S2** form). ‘Basically’ means that a system of prior authorisation has to be justified by reasons of justification accepted by the ECJ and it has to fulfil the requirements of proportionality.⁵⁷ As confirmed in the *Elchinov* case, there might be situations, where a person “for reasons relating to his state of health or to the need to receive urgent treatment in a hospital, was prevented from applying for such authorisation or was not able [...] to wait for the answer of the competent institution, of reimbursement from that institution in respect of such treatment”.⁵⁸ In addition, there might be a situation where prior authorisation has been refused in an unjustified way.⁵⁹ This interpretation of EU law by the ECJ can be helpful in **border regions** when in **critical situations** a person is transported to another MS and the authorisation is not given in advance but only afterwards (i.e. a the S2 form is issued retroactively). Presumably, this possibility was used in the Covid-19 **pandemic**.

Under the **PMD** (see Table 3) this is, basically, only the case for hospital and other treatment that subject to a certain degree of subject to planning requirements and related reasons. In other words, going to a dentist or a general practitioner in another MS can be done without prior authorisation.⁶⁰

⁵⁵ Cf. Art. 3 lit g PMD: ‘healthcare provider’ “means any [!] natural or legal person or any other entity legally providing healthcare on the territory of a Member State”.

⁵⁶ Case C-173/09 *Elchinov* ECLI:EU:C:2010:581, para 49: “legislation of a Member State cannot exclude, in all cases, reimbursement in respect of hospital treatment given in another Member State without prior authorisation”.

⁵⁷ Case C-173/09 *Elchinov* ECLI:EU:C:2010:581, para 44: “although European Union law does not preclude, in principle, a system of prior authorisation, it is nevertheless necessary that the conditions attached to the grant of such authorisation must be justified in the light of the imperatives mentioned above, that they do not exceed what is objectively necessary for that purpose and that the same result cannot be achieved by less restrictive rules. Such a system must, in addition, be based on objective, non-discriminatory criteria which are known in advance, in such a way as to circumscribe the exercise of the national authorities’ discretion, so that it is not used arbitrarily”.

⁵⁸ Case C-173/09 *Elchinov* ECLI:EU:C:2010:581, para 45.

⁵⁹ Case C-173/09 *Elchinov* ECLI:EU:C:2010:581, para 48: “where the request of an insured person for authorisation on the basis of that provision has been refused by the competent institution and it is subsequently established, either by the competent institution itself or by a court decision, that that refusal was unjustified, that person is entitled to be reimbursed directly by the competent institution in an amount equivalent to that which it would ordinarily have borne if authorisation had been properly granted at the outset”.

⁶⁰ According to Art. 9 para 5 PMD, MS can “offer patients a voluntary system of prior notification [!] whereby, in return for such notification, the patient receives a written confirmation of the amount to be reimbursed on the basis of an estimate”.

Table 3 – Prior authorisation under the PMD

	In general (Art. 8 para 2)	In a specific case (Art. 8 para 6)
Planning requirements	planning important for “balanced range of high-quality treatment”, to avoid waste of resources and allow for control of costs; - this includes hospital treatment with over-night stay - or treatment involving highly specialised and cost-intensive medical infrastructure or medical equipment (lit a)	-
Risks	treatments presenting a particular risk for patient or population (lit b)	unacceptable patient-safety risk , according to a clinical evaluation and with reasonable certainty; also considering potential benefit of healthcare for patient (lit a) substantial safety hazard (with reasonable certainty) for general public (lit b)
Concerns concerning providers	serious and specific concerns relating to the quality or safety of the care , on a case-by-case basis (lit c) ⁶¹	serious and specific concerns relating to the respect of standards and guidelines on quality of care and patient safety , including provisions on supervision (lit c) ⁶²
No undue delay	-	No undue delay ⁶³ according to ECJ case-law ⁶⁴ (lit d)

However, please note that in these situations, according to EU law, MS can - but do not have to - establish a system of prior authorisation. They can also do without it

⁶¹ Does not apply with in case of healthcare “which is subject to Union legislation ensuring a minimum level of safety and quality throughout the Union”; *ibid*.

⁶² No matter, “whether these standards and guidelines are laid down by laws and regulations or through accreditation systems established by the Member State of treatment”.

⁶³ I.e., “this healthcare can be provided on its territory within a time limit which is medically justifiable, taking into account the current state of health and the probable course of the illness of each patient concerned”.

⁶⁴ Case C-372/04 *Watts* ECLI:EU:C:2006:325, paras 68-79; para 68: “not exceed the period which is acceptable in the light of an objective medical assessment of the clinical needs of the person concerned in the light of his medical condition and the history and probable course of his illness, the degree of pain he is in and/or the nature of his disability at the time when the authorisation is sought”.

(hence, it is a possibility, **not an obligation**). There are several MS, which are not asking for prior authorisation although it would be possible under EU law.⁶⁵

The link between prior authorisation and **reimbursement** can be found in Art. 7 para 10 PMD, according to which cross-border healthcare shall be reimbursed if prior authorisation has been granted and according to this prior authorisation. Reimbursement is limited with the actual costs.⁶⁶ Besides the monetary perspective, in terms of the medical perspective it is up to the MSA to define the **basket of care**.⁶⁷ According to the PMD⁶⁸, **quality** of care, on the other hand, is to be determined by the MST (see below, in Chapter 5). The same is true for questions of **liability**.⁶⁹

The EU directive applies to both EU-MS and (within the EEA) to Norway, Iceland and Liechtenstein. It also refers to the special situation of **border regions**⁷⁰ as one of the situations, where presumably most cross-border healthcare takes place. While EU law, such as an EU directive, is binding law, this directive (because of the EU's lack of competence in this field) also includes provisions that are not binding. Chapter IV of the PMD (entitled '**cooperation** in healthcare') is less binding, as it simply 'invites' (but not forces) MS to act. The first topic in this Chapter IV is voluntary cooperation between MS, which can supplement the rights of individual patients.⁷¹

⁶⁵ According to Olsson, Smedt, and Wispelaere (2023), eight out of 24 MS (that have responded to this question) and Norway do not require prior authorisation (see p. 24 for further details). Czechia, for example, has no system of prior authorisation in place (p. 34).

⁶⁶ Cf. Art. 7 para 4: "without exceeding the actual costs of healthcare received".

⁶⁷ The "obligation to reimburse costs of cross-border healthcare should be limited to healthcare to which the insured person is entitled according to the legislation of the Member State of affiliation" (PMD, recital 13).

⁶⁸ The SSCR does not explicitly refer to quality. However, if the person is integrated into the system of the MST, the local quality standards also apply for this person. Applying a different (i.e. lower) level of quality would be an issue under the principle of non-discrimination.

⁶⁹ This applies both for information on liability (Art. 4 para 2 lit b PMD) and the setting up of systems of professional liability insurance (Art. 4 para 2 lit d PMD). For the SSCR, cf. Art. 85 para 2.

⁷⁰ See also below Chapter 4.2.

⁷¹ Two topics that will not be further covered in this report are health technology assessment (**HTA**) (see Commission Implementing Decision 2013/329/EU: Commission Implementing Decision of 26 June 2013 providing the rules for the establishment, management and transparent functioning of the Network of national authorities or bodies responsible for health technology assessment of 26 June 2013 providing the rules for the establishment, management and transparent functioning of the Network of national authorities or bodies responsible for health technology assessment, OJ 2013 L 175/71) and the **recognition of medical prescriptions** (see Commission Implementing Directive 2012/52/EU of 20 December 2012 laying down measures to facilitate the recognition of medical prescriptions issued in another Member State, OJ 2012 L 356/68). It should be mentioned briefly, that Art. 15 PMD on HTA **will be repealed** by Regulation (EU) 2021/2282 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 December 2021 on health technology assessment and amending Directive 2011/24/EU, OJ 2021 L 458/1.

Recital 50 PMD mentions that MS “should facilitate cooperation between healthcare providers, purchasers and regulators” of different MS “at national, regional or local level” with the aim to “ensure safe, high-quality and efficient cross-border healthcare”, especially “in border regions, where cross-border provision of services may be the most efficient [!] way of organising health services for the local population”. While it is mentioned as the most **efficient** way of providing health care, it requires “cooperation between the health systems” of different MS “on a sustained basis”. As this cooperation across borders with the aim to facilitate cross-border healthcare especially in border regions is voluntary⁷², MS can basically cooperate in various ways. The PMD (recital 50) names as some **examples** “joint planning, mutual recognition or adaptation of procedures or standards, interoperability of respective national information and communication technology (hereinafter ‘ICT’) systems, practical mechanisms to ensure continuity of care or practical facilitating of cross-border provision of healthcare by health professionals on a temporary or occasional basis”.

Chapter IV PMD also covers Art. 14 on **eHealth**. As already mentioned above, Chapter IV PMD ‘only’ includes voluntary cooperation between MS. Hence, Art. 14 PMD⁷³ covers a voluntary network⁷⁴ connecting national authorities responsible for eHealth. It is important to emphasise that these are public authorities, as opposed to private (or also public) healthcare providers, who are engaged in **‘telemedicine’**.⁷⁵ The EHDS proposal⁷⁶ defines ‘telemedicine’ as “the provision of healthcare services, including remote care and online pharmacies, through the use of information and communication technologies, in situations where the health professional and the patient (or several health professionals) are not in the same location”. It should be mentioned briefly, that the PMD also clarifies that in the case of ‘telemedicine’, healthcare is considered to be provided in the MS (i.e., MST) “where the healthcare provider is established” (Art. 3 lit d PMD). Back to Art. 14 PMD. This voluntary network shall aim at “delivering sustainable economic and social benefits of

⁷² In the same vein, recital 51 and Art. 10 para 3 PMD mention that the Commission shall “encourage” such cooperation between MS in border regions.

⁷³ It is planned that (similar to Art. 15 PMD on HTA, see note 71) Art. 14 PMD shall be replaced by the forthcoming rules on the European Health Data Space (EHDS); see Commission, Proposal for a regulation on the European Health Data Space, COM(2022) 197 final 3.5.2022.

⁷⁴ See also Commission Implementing Decision 2019/1765 of 22 October 2019 providing the rules for the establishment, the management and the functioning of the network of national authorities responsible for eHealth, and repealing Implementing Decision 2011/890/EU (notified under document C(2019) 7460), OJ 2019 L 270/83, as amended by OJ 2020 L1 227/1.

⁷⁵ Telemedicine can be seen as the narrower term compared to eHealth (in a similar way as patient mobility can be seen as the narrower term compared to cross-border healthcare, as the latter also includes telemedicine). While telemedicine is only about the doctor patient contact, eHealth also includes administrative coordination.

⁷⁶ Art. 2 para 2 lit l of the EHDS proposal (see note 73).

European eHealth systems and services and interoperable applications”, which aim especially at a high level of trust, security as well as continuity of care⁷⁷ (para 2 lit a). Amongst others, this network shall draw up guidelines on data to be shared in “patient’s summaries” (para 2 lit b) and support MS “in developing common identification and authentication measures to facilitate transferability of data in cross-border healthcare” (par 2 lit c). Due to the “limited effectiveness”, eHealth shall be strengthened by the upcoming EHDS proposal.⁷⁸

While the cross-border healthcare just mentioned refers to supporting (voluntary) measures of MS for planned healthcare, such **cooperation** can also make sense for **unplanned** care. Going back to Art. 168 para 7 TFEU, “the organisation and delivery of health services and medical care” is a competence the MS enjoy; hence, they can cooperate on a voluntary basis, even if not addressed by the PMD⁷⁹.

Although the **SSCR** requires prior authorisation as a default situation, the fact that it does not require up-front-payment (see above Table 2) can make it more attractive, especially if the treatment abroad is quite expensive. On the one hand (i.e. under the PMD), the patients must come up with the money themselves and then also live with the uncertainty of whether and when the money⁸⁰ will be reimbursed. Since chronologically the later legal act, the **PMD** (recital 28) refers to the **SSCR** and mentions that it does not affect an insured person’s right to seek treatment under the SSCR. Hence, patients have a right to choose between these two⁸¹ scenarios, the SSCR on the one side, and the PMD on the other side. Only an assessment of the individual situation of a particular situation can answer the question, which option is more attractive. MS have an obligation to reimburse according to the PMD or according to the SSCR, if the preconditions are fulfilled, unless the patient requests otherwise (recital 46, Art. 8 para 3 PMD).⁸²

⁷⁷ On continue of care, see also the medical records (defined in Art. 3 lit m PMD), addressed in the context of both the MST (Art. 4 para 2 lit f PMD) as well as the MSA (Art. 5 lit d PMD).

⁷⁸ EHDS proposal (see note 73), p. 2.

⁷⁹ It should be mentioned briefly, that the PMD is not about unplanned care, as it codifies the ECJ case-law on planned cross-border healthcare. Recital 28 PMD only briefly mentions that the PMD does not affect the rights of “an insured person’s rights in respect of the assumption of costs of healthcare which becomes necessary on medical grounds during a temporary stay in another Member State” according to the SSCR (i.e. unplanned care).

⁸⁰ At maximum up to the actual costs (recital 32 PMD).

⁸¹ Strictly speaking, besides those two scenarios of EU secondary law a patient could also rely on EU primary law, i.e. the freedom to receive (health) services in another MS (or the other three EEA/EFTA countries of Norway, Iceland and Liechtenstein). However, it is not likely that the ECJ would offer more or different rights compared to the existing ones of the SSCR or the PMD, where the latter summarizes its case-law (see also n 21).

⁸² Although they were designed for the SSCR, MS may also use the mechanisms of financial compensation between the competent institutions under the SSCR for the PMD. If a MS decides otherwise, it has to “ensure that patients receive reimbursement without undue delay” (Art. 9 para 5 [2] PMD).

In order to exercise the **right to choose** between these **two scenarios**, patients have to be aware of these two possibilities. However, it can be doubted that the requirement of the PMD, according to which in the context of **information provided** by the MSA on patients' rights and entitlements "a clear distinction shall be made between the rights which patients have by virtue of [the PMD] and rights arising from [the SSCR]" (Art. 5 lit b) is adhered to in practice. In addition, as Olsson et al. (2023) have shown in their report, some MS do not distinguish between cross-border healthcare under the SSCR and that taking place under the PMD. Consequently, if presumably, neither patients know about those two scenarios, nor **MS** distinguish and do not provide **corresponding data**, the question has to be addressed, if it would not make sense to merge these two legal documents. In order to avoid the burdensome situation of MS not implementing these changes in due time or correctly, the preferred option would be to **merge the two documents** by integrating the content of the PMD into the SSCR. The advantage of an EU regulation is that it has general application, is binding in its entirety and is directly applicable in all MS (Art. 288 para 2 TFEU).

2.3 Bilateral agreements and national law

Besides the two scenarios under EU law (see Table 2) depicted above in Chapter 2.2, there might be a different possibility (see Figure 1, below) according to (bilateral⁸³) agreements concluded between different MS. Such bilateral agreements have to provide more or different rights to patients, as they cannot amend existing rights under EU law. Hence, as the case might be, patients of MS that have concluded such **agreements** might have a **third possibility** (see Figure 1) concerning cross-border healthcare. Apart from that, **national law** (this would then be a **fourth possibility**) can also entitle patients to seek treatment abroad. Due to the primacy of EU law, this would have to grant additional rights. This could for example be the case for **rare diseases** where a country can send patients abroad for treatment that is usually not covered at home.

Especially for the above-mentioned special situation of **border regions** (see also below Chapter 4.2), it makes sense to bilaterally regulate the movement of patients in agreements between the official authorities of two MS on either side of the border.⁸⁴ Based on the primacy of EU law over conflicting national law, it goes

⁸³ These agreements could theoretically also be concluded between more than two MS (i.e., multilateral). Based on the constitutional law of the MS involved, this possibility can concern the whole territory of the MS concerned, or only one or several regions.

⁸⁴ Depending on the constitutional situation in either country, this can be a competence of the national and/or of the regional level.

without saying, that these **agreements** between MS⁸⁵ shall provide additional rights for patients within these border regions⁸⁶, but not restrict existing ones.

Source: own illustration

Figure 1 - Legal bases for patient mobility under EU law, agreements between MS and national law

For example, in the **Italian-Austrian border region**, such rules⁸⁷ provide for an additional possibility for patients from the Autonomous Province of Bolzano (who have their official residence in the Province of Bolzano and are registered with the Provincial Health Service). On the basis of an agreement in the Tyrolean hospitals, these patients can be treated for planned cases, e.g., in the hospital in Innsbruck, within the framework of the general fee class, i.e. not in a higher class (*Sonderklasse*), if they have received a pre-authorisation (an

⁸⁵ According to Art. 351 TFEU, agreements between one or more MS on the one hand, and one or more third countries on the other, concluded before 1 January 1958 in case of a founding MS (e.g., Germany), or before the date of the relevant accession (e.g., 1 May 2004 in case of Poland or Czechia, or 1 January 1995 in case of Austria), enjoy ‘priority’ in relation to the obligations stemming from the EU treaties. In case they are not compatible with the EU treaties, these MS “shall take all appropriate steps to eliminate the incompatibilities established”. For further details, see (Schmalenbach 2022) pp. 2633–2641.

⁸⁶ Of course, these agreements can also surpass a certain border region. By the way a term, which is not exactly defined, in terms of its geographical dimension.

⁸⁷ Cf. Decision of the Regional government of South Tyrol No 978 from December 1st 2020 (valid until end of 2023). In terms of legal quality, this can be qualified as an ‘agreement between the administration and private legal entities or other public administrations’ (*Vereinbarungen der Verwaltung mit privaten Rechtssubjekten oder anderen öffentlichen Verwaltungen*). N.B. As of mid-November 2023, a follow-up agreement is planned.

Ermächtigungsschein), in advance. However, these rules do not apply in the reverse situation (an Austrian seeking healthcare in this Italian region). Hence, such a situation would fall in a different scenario as those described above in Chapter 2.2.

3 Overview mobility flows

The **motivations** leading patients to move to another country are quite different and in some cases the legislation allows people, choosing alternative routes (even though the consequences in terms of waiting time and cost borne by the patient may be different).

As shown above, patients may move to another country because they reside in one country but are insured in another one: this is the case of transborder workers and pensioners which hold an S1 form, in some instances the form may also include relatives. Patients that do not fall into this group may move with a prior authorisation under the SSCR rules (in this case via the S2 form), they may move with (or according to national law without) prior authorisation using the PMD legislation, or there might be a unilateral/bilateral agreement that allows patients more freedom to move.

Data on patients' mobility across the EU is rather fragmented. To some extent, it reflects the differences in the legislation. However, it is the best tool to classify patient mobility across the EU. In what follows, we will not review only data on unplanned health care mobility. The most recent sources as concerns patients flow are represented by EU Publications Office (2023; EU Publications Office (2022), which allow to identify the flows for patients' mobility under S1 and S2 forms and Olsson, Smedt, and Wispelaere (2023) for data on patient moving under the PMD.

Let us start with **S1** holders, i.e. individuals registered for health care in one country but insured in another country. This form is issued mainly to cross-border workers (and their families) and mobile pensioners (and their families)⁸⁸ and approximately 0.4% of the insured persons reside in a Member State other than the competent one. In **2020**, the latest year for which data is available, between 1.7 and 1.9 million patients' residents in EU Member States were registered under the S1 form. Germany, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Switzerland, the UK and Austria were the main issuing countries; in fact, 70% of the forms were issued by these countries. For Luxembourg, more than 25% of the insured reside in another MS, while for the other issuing countries the impact is much lower (from 0.5% to 1%). As per the receiving MS, almost 25% of the persons with a valid S1 form reside in France. Furthermore, also Germany, Poland, Spain, Belgium and the Czechia received a high number of S1 (EU Publications Office of the European 2022; EU Publications Office 2023).

⁸⁸ See above, Chapter 2.2.2.

This data was significantly **lower** than in previous years, but in this case, the effect of Covid-19 is clearly important. A **rebound** seems to exist for **2021**: around 2.1 million persons resided in a Member State other than the competent Member State and were registered for healthcare in their Member State of residence by means of a portable document (PD) S1. This implies that on average 0.5 % of the insured persons resided in a Member State other than the competent Member State. About 2/3 of claimants were in working age while the rest were pensioners. For the latter one of the main flows is represented by UK pensioners moving to Spain. The total amount is about 0.25% of total EU healthcare spending (EU Publications Office 2022; EU Publications Office 2023).

For mobility falling under the S2 category, the number of **S2** forms (i.e. planned care under Art. 20 SSCR⁸⁹) issued and received decreased in 2020 compared to 2019 once again due to a possible Covid-19 effect. The strongest **decrease** as concerns the issue of S2 can be observed for Luxembourg (-73%), Austria (-75%), the Netherlands (-75%) and of course less patients were treated in the receiving countries (Switzerland, Austria, Luxembourg). There seems to have been a **rebound** from the serious drop in issued and received PDs S2 from 2019 to 2020. From 2020 to 2021 the number of issued PDs S2 increased by 0.3 %, while the number of received PDs S2 increased by 14.7 %. Luxembourg issued the highest number. The most important flows are from France to Belgium (12745 S2 forms), from Luxembourg to Germany (4859), from Luxembourg to Belgium (4723), and between Slovakia and the Czech Republic (1020). **¾ of treatments** were received in a **neighbouring** Member State and about 24% of individuals holding a S2 are resident in France (EU Publications Office of the European 2022; EU Publications Office 2023).; this may explain why France does not report data separately for people travelling under the PMD (Olsson, Smedt, and Wispelaere 2023). Less than 10 out of 100,000 EU citizens received care under S2. The total number of claims is 39,500 for about 131 million euro, i.e. about 0.013% of total health care benefit, which has increased to 0.2% in 2021 because of the increased mobility. A part of this flow originates also from bilateral agreements, but it is usually quite difficult to separate it because countries (the Netherlands and Germany, for example) do not report these data separately.

Finally, approximately 200 000 patients a year take advantage of the systems put in place under the **PMD** to receive healthcare treatment abroad: i.e. less than 0.05 % of EU citizens (Olsson, Smedt, and Wispelaere 2023). In recent years, France reported the highest number of **outgoing** patients and Spain the highest number of **incoming** patients. The majority of patient mobility has been between **neighbouring** MS (European Court of Auditors 2019). There were some exceptions as concerns patients driven mobility from northern countries to Spain. However,

⁸⁹ See above, Chapter 2.2.4.

the impact of the PMD seems to be rather limited especially in countries where patients had already challenged their health care system through appeal to the ECJ (Azzopardi-Muscat et al. 2018; Peralta-Santos and Perelman 2018).

EU patient mobility under the **PMD** has sensibly decreased in the past few years, both as concerns treatments subject to prior authorisation and those that do not require it. In 2018, the total amount reimbursed amounted to € 73.4 million; in 2019 it amounted to € 92.1 million, and in 2020 to € 77.5 million (Olsson, Smedt, and Wispelaere 2023). The share of the amount reimbursed concerning the PMD on the total government expenditure on healthcare amounts to 0.01%. This low share shows that the PMD only plays a small part in the total government expenditure on healthcare, but in spite of the results, cross-border health care has potentials as both concerns equity and efficiency, which deserve a further analysis.

4 Reasons for mobility

From a statistical point of view, planned cross-border health care falls into two **main categories**: the one originated by the **SSCR** (mainly under S1 and S2 forms) and the one originated under the **PMD** (see above). From an economic and behavioural point of view, mobility may derive from several **sources**, but from the point of view of our discussion, we will keep the distinction between planned and unplanned health care. **Unplanned** health care, which as mentioned above,⁹⁰ concerns treatment that becomes necessary on medical grounds during a temporary stay abroad (Art. 19 SSCR) and full healthcare (e.g. for posted workers) in case of Art. 17 (in the MS of residence) and Art. 18 SSCR (in the MSA).

Planned care derives from a specific choice of the patient to be treated abroad.⁹¹ This is the more heterogeneous category and also the one that is more interesting to study from an economic and legal point of view. Patients in this category may decide or need to be treated abroad because of a **rare disease**, to receive an innovative treatment that is delivered only in few specialised centres across Europe (cf. Chapter 4.1). They may seek treatment in border regions (cf. Chapter 4.2) often because of specific **agreements** between their country and the hosting one (cf. Chapter 2.3), or they may decide for **other reasons** that they want to be treated abroad (cf. Chapter 4.3). This latter type is what we could define the traditional patient mobility.

In addition to enlargement, also the economic **crises** place traditional patient mobility in a new context. Economic crises call for budget re-allocation or budget cuts, which often increase waiting time, and out-of-pocket payments. Since crises

⁹⁰ See above Chapter 2.2.1.

⁹¹ As mentioned above, planned care can take place based on Art. 20 SSCR (Chapter 2.2.3) or the PMD (Chapter 2.2.4).

do not hit countries in the same way, they produce significant differences on services provision on healthcare access (Karanikolos et al. 2013; Stuckler et al. 2011; McKee et al. 2012; Kentikelenis and Papanicolas 2012).

This impact on cost and waiting time is all the more remarkable, as those are the **key drivers** for travelling to another Member State for medical treatment (Peralta-Santos and Perelman 2018; Brouwer et al. 2003). Again, the picture of out-of-pocket medical expenditure, waiting times and, more generally, unmet health care needs varies between Member States (Glied 2008; OECD/European Union 2020).⁹²

According to data from the Eurobarometer (Peralta-Santos and Perelman 2018), about 50% of citizens across Europe would **consider the option** of being treated outside the boundaries, but in actual fact only a small fraction of patients is actually choosing to be treated outside and the numbers seem to decrease. This latter data may depend on the Covid-19 crisis, but it seems to have started before.

4.1 EU networks for treating rare diseases

According to the PMD, one of the **objectives** of European reference networks⁹³ is “to help realise the potential of European cooperation regarding highly specialised healthcare for patients and for healthcare systems by exploiting innovations in medical science and health technologies” (PMD Art. 12 para 2 lit a) (Héon-Klin 2017). The PMD **defines** a rare disease as any disease affecting fewer than five people in 10,000. An estimated 6,000 to 8,000 rare diseases affect between 6 % and 8 % of the EU population, i.e. between 27 and 36 million people (European Court of Auditors 2019). The specificities of rare diseases – a limited number of patients and a scarcity of relevant knowledge and expertise – led the Council of the EU to single out cooperation in this field as “as a unique domain of very high added value of action at Community level”. To this end, the EU has put in place several actions ranging from funds in research to strategies to develop new drugs to improving registry for rare diseases (Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety 2023b).

A recent study on the implementation of the PMD (EU Commission 2022) shows that **ERN are effective** in supporting the diagnosis and treatment of patients with rare and low prevalence complex diseases. Through training, development and

⁹² See above Chapter 1.2.

⁹³ See also Commission Delegated Decision 2014/**286**/EU of 10 March 2014 setting out criteria and conditions that European Reference Networks and healthcare providers wishing to **join** a European Reference Network must fulfil, OJ 2014 L 147/71; Commission Implementing Decision 2014/**287**/EU of 10 March 2014 setting out criteria for **establishing and evaluating** European Reference Networks and their Members and for facilitating the exchange of information and expertise on establishing and evaluating such Networks, OJ 2014 L 147/79, as amended by OJ 2019 L 200/35.

dissemination of guidelines and other materials, operational activities, and scientific and clinical cooperation, ERNs are providing healthcare professionals with access to a cross-border pool of expertise and knowledge. Considering that it has been less than five years since the ERNs have been established, the networks are creating a critical mass of patients' data through the patient registries, which are expected to provide a platform for research and lead to the collection and coordination of experience in treating patients with rare conditions requiring complex treatments. At present, there is not consensus in the literature on whether these networks are cost effective (Requena-Méndez et al. 2020). This is partly due to the fact that the number of patients is still small, while fixed costs for the network are quite high, but it is certainly a point requiring attention and further investigation.

The PMD sets up EU reference networks with the **aim** to improve diagnosis and treatment. At present, there are 952 providers across Europe, but the budget rules have not been set in a convincing manner and such mobility may be underfinanced (European Court of Auditors 2019). According to Eurodirs, a non-profit alliance of 970 rare disease patient organisations from 74 countries, despite the PMD in place to facilitate such collaboration, **obstacles** remain that not only make it difficult to access healthcare in another EU country, but leave the patient carrying the administrative, financial, and emotional burden to fight for and organise it.

In this case, **coordination** at EU level would allow treating more rare diseases. While at national level the development and the maintenance of an excellence centre to treat patients may not be cost effective (the sunk cost for the investment may be higher than the benefits), the use of the technology at EU level may allow sharing the costs and redressing the cost effective (C/E) ratio. Coordination at this level could also mean that more rare diseases can be treated since some countries may specialise in some of them, thus **avoiding cost replication**. Furthermore, countries with less technology/resources may benefit from their use, especially if the centres are financed at EU level and each country may send their patients to be treated free, or at marginal cost. In this context, the PMD had foreseen some initiatives to improve treatment.

People suffering from rare diseases scarcely have access to the right expertise and diagnostic infrastructure where they live, as healthcare systems face specific **challenges** in organising and delivering care due to their complexity and rarity. The needs of these extremely rare conditions are of such magnitude that they require greater cross-border healthcare **collaboration** to meet them. Furthermore, the idea of these networks is to improve **equity** across European regions. Small countries or those with a lower per capita GDP are deemed to invest less in the treatment of rare diseases, while these networks may allow enlarging access also

to patients living in less developed countries. The EU reference networks may also increase their importance and action by the use of **e-health** technologies. In fact, for some diseases the patient will be able to receive the state-of-the-art care in her own country, without the need to move. This may be done by sharing protocols among hospitals and health care centres also using the networks that have developed across EU countries.

This means that the **patients' best interests** are not always prioritised and results in a system that increases **inequalities**, because only the patients that are more prone to find information on their own will be able to use such opportunity. One of the most important hurdles in some cases is the absence of specific registers for patients that suffer from the same ailment. This information is in fact quite important, since it allows mapping the extent of the demand at EU level and it also allows studying this ailment. For some diseases the number of patients at national level is so small that it would be impossible to make an effective study of treatment alternatives; on the contrary, when **data is pooled** together it may well be possible that numbers allow to study the progress of the ailments in order to develop better treatment strategies. The development of this registry will also allow producing a detailed geographical map of the incidence of each disease, which will also allow distributing supply in a more rational way.

At present, the **role of patients** in this activity is rather **limited**, since most of these networks originate from collaborations between health care providers that share information and best practices across Europe. In the **future**, also patients may become more involved and may be allowed to look across Europe for providers also in the case of rare conditions.

The role of the national **information centre** in this context is quite important, as for other types of patient mobility.⁹⁴ With the advent of personalised medicine and the use of sophisticated technologies such as CAR-T⁹⁵, the treatments whose target

⁹⁴ Cf. Art. 6 PMD, national contact points for cross-border healthcare. MS shall establish one or more national contact points for cross-border healthcare, which shall consult with patient organisations, healthcare providers and healthcare insurers, as well as collaborate with other contact points and the European Commission. They shall exist both in the MST, where they shall provide information concerning healthcare providers, information on patients' rights, complaints procedures and mechanisms, etc., as well as in the MSA, where they shall provide patients and health professionals on patients' rights and entitlements to receive cross-border healthcare, in particular as regards the terms and conditions for reimbursement, etc. All the information to be provided shall be easily accessible and shall be made available by electronic means and in formats accessible to people with disabilities, as appropriate.

⁹⁵ One of the newest treatments for blood cancer is chimeric antigen receptor (CAR)-T cell therapy. These therapies use a body's own immune system to help fight cancer. In CAR-T

number of patients is below the threshold for being considered a rare disease⁹⁶ may be increasing and it may be even more important than in the past to create a network across Europe to treat these patients. At present the **strategy** is to finance providers, but it may well be that other strategies may prove to be more effective.

Financing providers has the advantage of avoiding replicating investments in sophisticated health technologies that for rare diseases may end up being used well below their full potential. A similar phenomenon has developed because of **hospital** competition and it is often defined as medical arm race. In this case, financing providers (hence avoiding competition through patient mobility) may allow cost containment.

An interesting development is the establishment of virtual consultation panels through the Clinical Patient Management System (**CPMS**). This is a dedicated IT platform and telemedicine tool, developed by the Commission to allow healthcare providers from all over the EU to work together virtually to diagnose and treat patients, which are however underused because of the lack of integration with National Health Care system and administrative long procedures, which make the instrument not cost effective at present. The Covid-19 experience may however create a boost for these activities since patients are now more aware and experienced in the use of virtual consultations.

4.2 Border region patient mobility

A specific area where patient mobility is already in place, but could further be developed, is across **neighbouring regions**.⁹⁷ Specific patterns have already developed through time, but in other cases barriers still exist to the exploitation of the potentials of cross border mobility, which could instead improve both access to

cell therapies, T cells are taken from the patient's blood and are changed in the lab by adding a gene for a receptor (called a chimeric antigen receptor or CAR), which helps the T cells attach to a specific cancer cell antigen. The CAR-T cells are then given back to the patient.

⁹⁶ The European Union considers a disease as rare when it affects less than 1 in 2,000 citizens. See <https://www.eurordis.org/information-support/what-is-a-rare-disease/#:~:text=The%20European%20Union%20considers%20a,1%5D>.

⁹⁷ One important finding of the two field trips to Gmünd / Austria (September 4th and 5th 2023) and Furth im Wald / Germany (September 11th and 12th 2023) was that cross-border cooperation in border regions ideally starts with **emergency care**, allowing ambulances, if necessary, to also operate on the other side of the border. A next step can consist in enabling also **planned** care, i.e. allowing patients to access healthcare (in- and or outpatient) on the other side of the border. A third step can consist in creating a **joint centre** located close to the border (e.g. in Gmünd). One possibility, that we have not yet encountered would be joint **planning of capacities** on either side of a border. On health-related challenges in border regions, see also European Parliament resolution of 11 September 2018 on boosting growth and cohesion in EU border regions (2018/2054(INI)), OJ 2019 C 433/24, pts. 10 and 21.

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care (by also reducing unmet needs indicators) and could also allow to rationalise health care expenditure by reducing excess capacity. This mobility may originate for several reasons: it may be determined by the fact that some people may live in a country that is different from the one they work (i.e. full healthcare, respectively S1 form, as covered in Chapter 2.2.2). This is especially true for the **Benelux** area, where cross-border work is quite common and it reaches also some areas of France, Germany, Austria and Eastern Europe. In this case, patient mobility derives from **institutional factors**, health information, network, standing agreements between purchasers and providers. For countries, where health care is financed through some form of **social insurance** or for jobs where supplementary insurance at firm level is quite common, the payer for health care may not necessarily be the national one (i.e., the one where the individual is resident). In this case, this is a sort of apparent mobility (health care is financed in the same country where it is delivered). In some of the countries considered, health care is financed by the **public** sector, but through a system of either **private** insurance (as in the Netherlands) or social insurance (as in Germany and partially in France). In this case, a perfect separation exists between the **purchaser** and the **provider**; in other words, the purchaser, not being itself provider of health care, has less constraints in negotiating care with outside providers: the main hurdle in this case is the price difference. Also, and perhaps more important, countries that have stipulated bilateral agreements, which allows border patients to move with more freedom, are quite similar as concerns income and prices. This implies that also health care costs across these countries are probably rather similar so that the national purchaser is more inclined to let patients be treated abroad.

Big data and new statistics available at NUTS2 level may however help the EU to play a more active role in this context. By crossing unmet needs in border regions with data on available health technologies, some possible patterns of patients' flow may be identified where mobility could improve welfare.

Mobility may also originate because of **historical**⁹⁸ reasons: one of the most interesting examples is the split of **Czechoslovakia** into two separate countries that before were sharing health care provisions. Mobility in this case originates from well-established pattern of health care supply and also from the fact that, as some recent studies show (Mullan, Wilson, and Guillermo-Ramirez 2022), patient are quite reluctant to change a health care provider, especially when their past experience has been positive. This type of mobility is due to decrease through time since new patterns will soon emerge. Other reasons such as language proximity may instead be more important in the long run.

⁹⁸ Another example is patient mobility between North Tyrol (Austria) and South Tyrol (Italy).
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Finally, cross-border mobility derives from **proximity**: in some cases, the closest hospital is the one across the border or because of waiting times. (Mullan, Wilson, and Guillermo-Ramirez 2022) examine four case studies, each one showing interesting characteristics. They are:

1. Meuse Rhine
2. Grand Est (France) - Luxembourg
3. Lower Austria/South Bohemia/Slovakia
4. Poland/Czechia

The (ad 1) **Meuse Rhine** flow mostly originates from German patients that go to the Netherlands because of proximity of a hospital located across the border. For German patients, specialist care is often more accessible in the Netherlands rather than in Germany. Several agreements regulate these flows, but the regions have not been able to produce reliable data on payments and reimbursements so that is difficult to assess the cost of care across the borders. It is interesting to note that both Germany and the Netherlands rely on a system of private purchasers (although care is publicly financed), something that probably makes reimbursements across the border. When the separation between purchasing and providing functions is not so clear-cut, patient mobility may find more hurdles.

The (ad 2) flow of patients between **Luxembourg and France** mostly originates from the mobility between the two countries deriving from family and professional reasons (hence, presumably mainly solved by the S1 form⁹⁹): it is estimated that Luxembourg workforce is represented by about 43.7% of cross-border workers in 2020. This includes both those living in a border region, and others such as the Portuguese who represent more than 11% of the Luxembourg workforce (Mullan, Wilson, and Guillermo-Ramirez 2022).

Cross-border mobility originates, because quite a few patients do not live in the country where they work, given the proximity. In other cases, mobility originates for **specific treatments** such as chemotherapy (from France to Luxembourg) and dialysis¹⁰⁰. Furthermore, many doctors in Luxembourg have undertaken some or all of their training in France and have developed professional relationships in France, where they refer patients for oncology and other complex diseases.

In the case of (ad 3) **Lower Austria/South Bohemia/Slovakia**, although all types of care are accessed, the focal point is around maternal and neonatal care. Pregnancy and birth were the single biggest treatment, but the biggest patient group was from the United Arab Emirates, hence a third country. Cross-border care is

⁹⁹ As mentioned above, this allows for full coverage in both countries (see Chapter 2.2.2).

¹⁰⁰ On dialysis and chemotherapy that can fall within 'unplanned care', see above at note 34.

influenced by local proximity to care, both specialist and routine. The historical context in this case is important: some cities that were previously in the same countries have now moved to others, thus creating mobility among the population based on a shared history. Data on patient mobility in 2019 shows that Slovakia is a relatively high user of the PMD (about 10,000 patients travelling, of whom 5,000 travelled to Czechia for care not requiring prior authorization), Czechia however reported in total only 916 reimbursements not requiring prior authorization and Austria only seven in total, not requiring prior authorization. Concerning the SSCR, Czechia and Slovakia are relatively small users, but Austria reported issuing 4,489 S2 forms for Germany, accounting for 13% of all S2 forms issued in 2019. Austria and Czechia report very limited use of the SSCR, with Austria reporting six S2 forms for care in Czechia and none for care in Slovakia; Czechia issued 62 S2 forms for care in Slovakia; and Slovakia issued 855 S2 forms for care in Czechia. Finally, Austrian insurers have collected data on all care provided in 2020 in the 25 hospitals of lower Austria to patients not holding Austrian insurance. These data show that 19,632 patients not insured in Austria received care in a hospital in Lower Austria.

In case of (ad 4) **Poland and Czechia**, most of the mobility derives from Poland, sending their patients to Czechia. Both countries did not report to have issued or received any S2 claim in 2019. Czechia made 916 reimbursements for planned care under the PMD in 2019, of which the majority (539) went to Germany; only 17 reimbursements for care in Poland were reported. Poland reported 15,574 reimbursements of which 14,171 were for care in Czechia.¹⁰¹

4.3 Patients driven mobility (without bilateral agreements)

Already the PMD¹⁰² seems to depart from the idea that the impetus for cross-border healthcare is based on the patient's decision. As depicted above in Figure 1, patients can have several possibilities to seek treatment abroad, provided that there are also bilateral agreements. While these agreements might most often affect border regions (see above Chapter 4.2), we want to focus in the following on patient mobility that takes place **outside** such **bilateral agreements**. In other words, based on existing EU law (SSCR or PMD), this mobility originates from patients that decide to be treated outside their country simply because they look for a better alternative

¹⁰¹ Poland reports that it operates a parallel national system for care in another country. On the basis of national legislation, Poland sends patients for planned medical treatment abroad, if the treatment is not performed in Poland, but the treatment is necessary for the patient in his/her health condition, and if the treatment is included in the medical services provided for by the legislation of Poland. Public or private healthcare providers may provide such treatment.

¹⁰² Recital 11: "individual patients who decide to seek healthcare in a Member State other than the Member State of affiliation".

to what is supplied in their country.¹⁰³ The **reason** may be determined by the fact that care abroad may be **timelier**, or more **appropriate** to their needs.

For this treatment, the PMD¹⁰⁴ allows in certain situations¹⁰⁵ for a system of **prior authorisation**. According to EU law, prior authorisation is not mandatory, but just a possibility. As mentioned above, some Member States do require prior authorisation, while others do not. However, some countries (France for example) fail to distinguish between patient driven mobility and the one that stems from agreements with neighbouring countries. Finally, some countries do not report the number of authorisations granted so that data on patients' mobility is not very accurate (Olsson, Smedt, and Wispelaere 2023).

According to the latest figures (Olsson, Smedt, and Wispelaere 2023), in 2021 the number of patients that receive care outside their country of residence was about 3,667 (out of the 5,409) for mobility subject to prior authorisation (but this data covers 15 MS and the UK). The number of requests that do not require prior authorisation is sensibly higher: 191,000 and about 155,500 granted. The **trend** is decreasing in the last years probably due to the Covid-19 pandemic. France is one of the countries that contributes more to this mobility, but the **quality of the data** does not allow making a ranking of countries, because for France data for mobility originates from collaborations among health care systems from border-region patient mobility. France, Poland and Denmark are the countries with the highest number of authorisations¹⁰⁶, while the countries with the highest destinations are Spain, Portugal and Belgium. Most of this mobility is directed towards border countries with the exception of a significant flow from northern countries (Sweden, Norway, and Denmark) to Spain. Part of this mobility may perhaps originate from patients that are still formally resident in these countries, but that spend a significant part of their life in the south of Europe and do not use a S1 or S2 form.

The picture, as shown in Chapter 3 should also take into account patients travelling under S2 form since for some of them the use of S2 or the PMD rules are interchangeable, although the financial consequences and the procedure is different, as shown above. In this respect, such mobility is increasing again after Covid-19, but seems to follow very specific patterns, as also shown above.

¹⁰³ Of course, this type of patient mobility without such a bilateral agreement can (and often will) affect border regions.

¹⁰⁴ Under the SSCR, prior authorization is always necessary for planned care (cf. Art. 20 SSCR).

¹⁰⁵ See above, Table 3.

¹⁰⁶ However, for France it is difficult to know what originates this mobility flow.

Such mobility can originate from **quality** of care¹⁰⁷ **differences** across countries, where the term quality has to be interpreted in a rather broad sense. In this context, in fact quality means both medical **quality** (i.e., the type of treatment path that is offered in each country for a specific disease), **waiting times** (the time that is necessary to wait before being treated), accessibility time (especially in border regions)¹⁰⁸ and it may also originate from a **specific type** of treatment. In the latter case, some countries decide not to offer in spite of the latter being appropriate for the type of ailment.

The basic idea is that such patient mobility should allow in the **short run** more mobile individuals, usually those with a higher willingness to pay and travel to receive better care abroad. In the **long run**, however, such mobility should spur incentives for their home country to improve **quality** of care so that in the future also patients that are not able to travel will be able to benefit from such initial choice. However, this mechanism is **welfare improving**, only if in the long run the quality gap across countries decreases, otherwise patient mobility may in fact increase disparities both across countries and across individuals in the same country (Siciliani and Straume 2019; Sá, Siciliani, and Straume 2019; Brekke, Straume, and Siciliani 2018; Levaggi and Levaggi 2014; Brekke et al. 2014; 2016; Berta, Guerriero, and Levaggi 2021). The explanation for this can be found in the following fact. For a health care system under financial pressure it may be more convenient to buy better care to the few asking to go abroad, compared to providing a better average level to the population as a whole.

Andritsos and Tang (2014) examine the role of patient mobility on waiting times using a **model** where health care can be measured using two characteristics: quality and waiting times. A regulator wants to increase quality and reduce waiting times by allowing patients to receive care in a neighbour region. From a benchmark solution where the level of quality is fixed, but the waiting time may induce some patients to give up treatment, the authors examine **optimal market entry** by a cross country provider that supplies care with the same quality level with an extra co-payment, but without delay. In this setting, the regulator has to find the **optimal waiting time and reimbursement** rate that maximise welfare. The model shows that if some conditions are met, welfare can improve and costs are reduced if the regulator opens the market cross border mobility. In general, the welfare effects of patient mobility across regions are not clear-cut. Brekke et al. (2014) use a **spatial competition framework** with two regions, where health care quality is decided at regional level (to maximise regional welfare) and patients may be

¹⁰⁷ See below Chapter 5.

¹⁰⁸ This can especially be the case in the so-called 'Šluknov Hook', an area between the Saxon towns of Sebnitz and Seifhennersdorf, which is almost completely surrounded by Germany.

allowed to choose freely between the providers in the two regions, which differ in their ability to supply high-quality care. They show that cross border patient mobility may be **beneficial for both** patients from high and low skill regions as in the classical **Heckscher–Ohlin model** of international trade¹⁰⁹. Patients from high skill regions receive benefits from high skill hospitals, while patients in the low skill regions that value **quality** may receive their preferred level in the other region. However, these effects also depend on the **price** chosen for cross-border mobility. In fact, if the price is too low, the competition will drive quality down. This is an important point from a policy point of view. The present regulation foresees that the provider is paid the **same** price as for national patients (unless there are specific agreements with the purchaser, which may well be possible for health care systems where purchasers and providers are somehow private/non-profit organisations). The PMD also foresees that the country where the patient is resident is paying the **lowest** between the price paid to national providers and the price in the other country. This of course means that if the cross-border price is higher, the patient has to pay for the difference (on top of other private expenses). This raises **barriers** to cross-border patient mobility and also creates equity issues, since only patients that can afford the cost are able to travel abroad.

Another important dimension that should be considered is represented by the **institutional setting** in which such mobility takes place, especially as concerns the level of **vertical integration** in health care provision. Bisceglia, Cellini, and Grilli (2018) consider the effects of the interactions among regional purchasers, which are clearly separated entities from the providers. This setting allows consideration of providers that compete both for **intra-regional** and **extra-regional** mobility and show that the optimal regulated price is higher in the region with the more efficient providers; this implies higher expenditure but higher patients' welfare, a result that is confirmed by the empirical literature (Berta, Guerriero, and Levaggi 2021) As shown above, this is certainly one of the most favourable scenarios for patient mobility to take place, since purchasers by not being integrated with health care providers are less interested in health provision planning.

Patient mobility may however have **countervailing effects on welfare** when regions with a different level of income compete (Brekke et al. 2016). They develop a **model** with **three regions** that **differ** in the distribution of **income**, so that there

¹⁰⁹ The Heckscher–Ohlin model shows the benefits for trade also in a context where one country has more resources than another one. They consider a two-country model, where two goods/resources are produced. Country 1 has an endowment higher than 2 for both commodities. However, the model shows that if country 2 has a better relative allocation of one of the two resources, trade may be profitably exploited by both countries. As per cross-border mobility, the idea is that patients moving will increase competition for service provision so that the quality will increase also in the low skill region.

is a high-income, a middle-income, and a low-income region. In each region, patients will only travel to a neighbouring region if the health care quality difference is sufficiently large to offset travel costs, co-payments and possibly some search costs. Individuals have decreasing marginal utility of income, which implies that the marginal cost of raising tax revenues decreases with average income: in other words, in countries with higher income the willingness to pay for better health care is higher. Health care **quality** is increasing in income, implying patient mobility from lower income to higher income regions. High-income regions only import patients and are usually better off, if the cross-border price is at least equal to their marginal cost. Low-income regions export patients, while middle income may simultaneously import and export patients. From a welfare point of view, this implies that cross-border patient mobility may have adverse effects on health care quality and welfare, particularly in low- and middle-income regions. Another important element that may determine the welfare effects of mobility is represented by the role of institutional settings.

Aiura (2019) considers a model, where regions differ in **income**, but **taxes** are progressive, but their results are in line with this observation. In this setting patients' mobility has no effect on the quality of the richer (and more efficient) region, but it reduces quality in the less rich (less efficient) ones that may find more profitable to send patients to be treated abroad instead of offering treatment in the country of residence.

Finally, it is also important to consider **efficiency and equity** aspect. The literature has in fact shown that while quality may improve because of competition, quality gaps may instead increase.

(Siciliani and Straume (2019) examine **equity** issues by studying quality levels in a market where patients' evaluation of health care benefits depends on the severity of their illness and competing hospitals have different levels of efficiency. The authors examine two sources of inequality: the first one, which could be defined '**postcode inequality**', arises from the fact that a patient living close to a low-quality hospital has to travel more to receive a high standard of care. The second source derives from the **severity of patients' illness**. The authors show that because of competition, quality gaps may increase or decrease, a result similar to Brekke et al. (2016). In this case, postcode inequality is certainly increasing (and the converse is true: if the quality gap decreases because of competition, postcode inequality shrinks). When equity is evaluated across heterogeneity in illness severity, the effects are less clear and do not necessarily go in the same direction as the difference in hospital quality (i.e., an increase in the quality gap may also lead to a reduction in ex-post health outcomes). This means that equity is another important

dimension in the evaluation of patient mobility and that it may not be simply evaluated in terms of quality and quality gaps.

In the long-run, this type of mobility should disappear: competition should provide a strong incentive to stimulate quality improvements in the less efficient jurisdictions but this result is not so clear-cut (Brekke et al. 2012).

Bisceglia, Cellini, and Grilli (2019) extend the results presented in a **static** framework by Bisceglia, Cellini, and Grilli (2018) on decentralisation and quality choices across regions to a dynamic context and show that permanent **differences in quality** may persist, even in the presence of a large degree of symmetry in parameters across regions. In their context a key role is played by regulators, as their policies may reduce or enlarge the gap.

The empirical evidence that shows that in some contexts, mobility has allowed reducing the gap, confirms the findings of the theoretical literature. However, in others it seems to have enhanced the differences. Quality gaps appear to be related to the size of the income difference (see for example, for Italy, (Balía, Brau, and Moro 2020) and this calls for more research into the role of institutional settings.

The literature suggests that patients' free choice between types (public vs. private), and across providers in different regional jurisdictions has not a clear effect on quality and efficiency. Gravelle et al.(2014) show that hospital quality, measured using medical and patient reported indicators, is positively affected by the quality provided by other hospitals in the same market. This finding is in line with other literature showing that patients' choice enhances competition, improves the quality of health care services, and also allows a containment of costs (Oliver and Mossialos 2005; Gaynor and Town 2011; Moscelli et al. 2018). Some argue that the PMD has not reached the results that were sought (Riedel 2016; Azzopardi-Muscat et al. 2018). Several Member State have tried to reduce it, especially after the so-called *Petru*¹¹⁰ case (Frischhut and Levaggi 2015). Members States are reluctant to increase patient mobility for two main reasons.

- The **cost** to finance such expenses may reduce the resources available for domestic patients and since the barriers to mobility are quite important, this may reduce **equity** in access to quality of care across socio-economic classes. To reduce this problem, the PMD has determined that patients wanting to be treated abroad will be reimbursed the lowest price between the actual cost and the national tariff. This system may however make it very hard for some people to move. Furthermore, when this mobility is strictly across the borders it may create serious barriers to access health care.

¹¹⁰ Case C-268/13 *Petru* ECLI:EU:C:2014:2271.

- Patient mobility causes **extra** cost to health care systems. Since patient mobility cannot be foreseen, each Member State has to provide care for all the residents, but only a part of them will use health care.

However, when cross border mobility is driven by unmet needs (as in the case where care is more easily available in another country because of the location of domestic and foreign health care centres), the use of the reimbursement rules set up by the PMD may be rather restrictive and may also create equity problems. Mobility in this case is often one direction and usually from a lower to a higher income country. In this case also Purchasing Power Parities (PPP) play an important role in cost determination and making patients pay the difference in cost may lead to equity issues (only richer individuals may afford the expenditure). At present one of the ways patients may use to solve this problem is to use the S1 form (under the SSCR), which allows to be fully reimbursed, but of course it requires a somehow more complicated process. In this area, the EU may certainly be able to regulate better these local situations, starting from assessing a European standard price for at least the most common treatments that could be used as reference for regulating mobility in countries where PPP are quite high.

5 Quality of care

Over the past few years with increasing numbers of people traveling across borders to seek medical treatment, the **medical tourism** industry has experienced substantial growth, both outside Europe for hospital treatment and within Europe for private treatments that are not publicly financed (Beukers, Kemp, and Varkevisser 2014; Varkevisser and van der Geest 2007). This is a well-developed phenomenon in countries such as the U.S., where high medical costs have made private insurances offer lower premia to their insurers, if they are open to travel abroad for some treatments. However, as the industry expands, ensuring the **quality and safety** of healthcare services becomes crucial, as the health sector is “a sector well known for information asymmetry”¹¹¹. Quality in health care is in fact difficult to be observed for each patient since it may be difficult to determine the actual health gain; even when it is observable it is not verifiable before a Court (Aghion and Holden 2011), i.e. it is not possible to define a set of objective indicators that can be written in a contract.

Across the EU, countries measure quality using **different indicators**, which does not allow to make a straightforward comparison. Beaussier et al. (2020) examine the process to determine quality of care in four countries (Germany, the UK, France and the Netherlands) and show that even in a context of geographical and cultural

¹¹¹ Recital 43 PMD.

proximity, quality of care is assessed in a very different way even for a more homogeneous service such as hospital care. Only safety appears to be a shared priority, other dimensions are instead more heterogeneous. The UK relies on a very broad definition of quality, with a focus on hospital management. The situation is almost the opposite in Germany, where most indicators focus on clinical excellence and practitioners' adoption of best medical practices. Similarly to the UK, in France, quality is mostly measured at the hospital level, rather than at the service level and does not assess the skills of individual clinicians while the Netherlands are more similar to the German system.

In the absence of uniform indicators, **perceived quality** becomes important. (Eurofund 2019) classify health care system using data from the European Quality of Life Survey (EQLS) 2016, carried out in 28 EU Member States (i.e. before Brexit), which collected detailed data on perceived quality of primary care and specialist or hospital care in particular. They conclude that only five health care systems (Austria, Denmark, Finland, Luxembourg and Sweden) have high performance on all quality dimensions. Belgium, Czechia, Estonia, France, Germany, Ireland, Lithuania, Malta, the Netherlands, Slovenia, Spain and the UK have high performances on some indicators and low on others¹¹², while another group of countries (Bulgaria, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Poland, Portugal and Slovakia) have a general low level of performances with some exceptions. For a final group of countries (Croatia, Cyprus, Greece and Romania) all the indicators are low.

For this reason, standards of quality across countries and health care providers are quite important. In the U.S., the problem has been partially solved through accreditation. For the EU, quality is still assessed with national rules, which are often difficult to be compared as shown above.

Patients' choices at national level are often driven by reputation and other patients experience (Varkevisser and Van der Geest 2007; Beukers, Kemp, and Varkevisser 2014; Varkevisser, van der Geest, and Schut 2012), even in the presence of quality **indicators**, which are often difficult to be interpreted (Varkevisser, van der Geest, and Schut 2012; Gutacker et al. 2016). For treatments abroad, such indicators may be difficult to be obtained and also word-of-mouth may play a marginal role given the limited number of patients that use this alternative.¹¹³

In the U.S., **accreditation** plays a significant role in addressing these concerns and has a direct impact on the reputation and credibility of medical tourism

¹¹² Belgium and the Netherlands do better on primary care than specialist or hospital care, while for Malta and the UK the opposite is true.

¹¹³ On the response of the PMD to this challenge, see below at note 126.

destinations. In the EU context, there is not yet a clear framework for quality evaluation, especially at super-national level. Some countries have started local initiative aimed at improving quality, but there does not seem to be a clear direction as far as the EU is concerned. Although it is not clear how quality indicators are interpreted by patients in their choice of the provider (Gutacker et al. 2016; Moscelli et al. 2018), quality is a very important aspect to be taken into account for cross border patients.

The importance of quality of care has been emphasized by the **ECJ** for instance in the context of national prior authorisation requirements for hospital treatment, where **planning requirements** can be legitimate, as they seek “to achieve the aim of ensuring that there is sufficient and permanent access to a balanced range of **high-quality** hospital treatment in the State concerned”¹¹⁴. This statement has to be seen against the background of Art. 168 para 1 TFEU, according to which a “**high level** of human health protection shall be ensured in the definition and implementation of all Union policies and activities”.¹¹⁵ It should be mentioned briefly, that in this context high level does not mean “highest level”.¹¹⁶

In this context, MS do enjoy some **discretion**, as the ECJ has consistently held that “health and life of humans rank foremost among the assets and interests protected by the Treaty and [therefore] it is for the Member States to determine the **level** of protection which they wish to afford to public health and the **way** in which that level is to be achieved”¹¹⁷.

This discretion, however, finds its **limitation** in case of possible controversies with regard to quality issues. For example, the question can arise, if certain treatment is considered “state-of-the-art”, or only as experimental. In a case from 2001, that is to say already before the PMD was adopted, the ECJ has neither pointed to the MSA, or to the MST to answer this question, but to “what is considered normal according to the state of **international** medical science and medical standards generally accepted at international level”¹¹⁸. In this context, the ECJ has emphasized the need that treatment has to be “sufficiently tried and tested”¹¹⁹ and that account has to be

¹¹⁴ Case C-157/99 *Smits and Peerbooms* ECLI:EU:C:2001:404, para 78 (emphasis added); Case C-173/09 *Elchinov* ECLI:EU:C:2010:581, para 43.

¹¹⁵ Emphasis added. For further details, see Frischhut, (2017).

¹¹⁶ See Frischhut, (2017), p. 65 and Case T-177/13 *TestBioTech and Others v Commission* ECLI:EU:T:2016:736, para 106 (“That high level does not necessarily, in order to be compatible with that provision [i.e. TFEU Article 168(1)], have to be the highest technically possible [...]”).

¹¹⁷ Case C-171/07 *Apothekerkammer des Saarlandes and Others* ECLI:EU:C:2009:316, para 19, emphases added.

¹¹⁸ Case C-157/99 *Smits and Peerbooms* ECLI:EU:C:2001:404, para 92, emphasis added. See also now, recital 22 PMD.

¹¹⁹ *Ibid*, para 94.

taken of “existing scientific literature and studies, the authorised opinions of specialists [etc.]”^{120,121} Hence, the Court has emphasized requirement of evidence-based decisions.

Within these guidelines of high-quality of care and MS’ discretion how to achieve this goal (including the limitation of the ‘international state-of-the-art), the **PMD**¹²² does not provide a lot of substantive clarification¹²³. However, (for reasons of a lack of EU competence in this field) it simply allocates the task for defining further details to one of the two MS involved in the movement of a patient (i.e., from the MSA to the MST). According to Art. 4 para 1 lit b PMD¹²⁴, it is the obligation of the **MST** to define “standards and guidelines on quality and safety laid down by the Member State of treatment”¹²⁵. The obligation regarding the information to be provided by **healthcare providers** is addressed as follows. According to Art. 4 para 2 lit b PMD, “healthcare providers provide relevant **information** to help individual patients to make an **informed choice**, including on treatment options, on the availability, quality and safety of the healthcare they provide in the Member State of treatment and that they also provide clear **invoices** and clear information on **prices**, as well as on their authorisation or registration status, their insurance cover or other means of personal or collective protection with regard to professional **liability**. To the extent that healthcare providers already provide patients resident in the Member State of treatment with relevant information on these subjects, this Directive does not oblige healthcare providers to provide more extensive information to patients from other Member States”¹²⁶.

While these provisions strive to enhance quality in patient mobility, quality concerns can also lead to a situation, where based on quality issues MS are allowed to **impede** planned treatment abroad. This is true both for healthcare that **in general** can be subject to prior authorisation (some planning necessary to ensure high-quality treatment; risks for patient or population; providers giving rise to concerns relating to quality of safety; Art. 8 para 2 PMD), as well as for refusing prior authorisation in a **particular situation** (patient exposed to safety risk; safety hazards for general public; providers giving rise to concerns relating to quality of safety, etc.;

¹²⁰ Ibid, para 98.

¹²¹ It should be mentioned briefly, that this case-law of the ECJ (for the EU) has also been applied by the EFTA Court for the EFTA/EEA countries, that is to say, Norway, Iceland and Liechtenstein: Joined Cases E-11/07 and E-1/08 *Rindal and Slinning* [2008] EFTA Ct. Rep. 320. See also Frischhut (2020).

¹²² For quality issues concerning blood, tissues and cells, and organs, see Frischhut, (2017), pp. 81-84.

¹²³ See also Frischhut, (2017) p. 77. On some soft-law clarifications, see below at note 132.

¹²⁴ This resonates what the ECJ had already decided earlier: Case C-444/05 *Stamatelaki* ECLI:EU:C:2007:231, para 37; see also Frischhut, (2017) pp. 74-75.

¹²⁵ Subject to the limitations of the international state-of-the-art.

¹²⁶ Emphases added.

Art. 8 para 6 PMD). For all these single reasons a certain **threshold** (risk not acceptable; substantial hazard; serious concerns) as well as an **evidence-based decision** (according to clinical evaluation; reasonably certainty; specific concerns) are required.¹²⁷

Turning back to the provisions of the **PMD supporting quality** of care, one can name the following rules: rules on follow-up treatment (Article 5 lit c), on medical records (Article 5 lit c), as well as on national contact points (Art. 6), which have to provide “upon request, relevant information on the standards and guidelines” concerning quality and safety, as laid down by the MST (Art. 4 para 2 lit a).¹²⁸ While these provisions of the PMD belong to its binding parts, some tools that support quality of care in patient mobility can also be found in Chapter IV of the PMD (entitled ‘cooperation in healthcare’), which – as mentioned earlier – is less binding. In this latter field, MS are simply ‘invited’ (but not forced) to act.¹²⁹

One such ‘encouraged’ field of **cooperation**¹³⁰ amongst MS includes “cooperation on standards and guidelines on quality and safety” (Art. 10 para 1). As mentioned above, voluntary **European reference networks** (ERN) shall be established “in particular in the area of rare diseases”¹³¹. In this context, the PMD addresses as one of the objectives to be achieved by an ERN the necessity “to encourage the development of quality and safety benchmarks and to help develop and spread best practice within and outside the network” (Art. 12 para 2 lit g PMD).

Quality of care is also mentioned in EU **soft-law** (i.e. not legally binding), in the so-called ‘Council Conclusions on Common **values and principles** in European Union Health Systems’.¹³² This document issued by the Health Ministers at the time established the “overarching **values** of *universality, access to good quality care, equity, and solidarity*”.¹³³ “Beneath these overarching values”, there is also a set of

¹²⁷ See Frischhut, (2017), pp. 78-79.

¹²⁸ One can also name, in this context, transparent complaints procedures, systems of professional liability insurance, and medical records (Article 4 para 2 (c), (d) and (f)).

¹²⁹ See Frischhut, (2017), pp. 79-81.

¹³⁰ See also recital 50 PMD: “Member States should facilitate cooperation between healthcare providers, purchasers and regulators of different Member States at national, regional or local level in order to ensure safe, high-quality and efficient cross-border healthcare”.

¹³¹ Art. 13 and recitals 54-55 PMD. N.B. A rare disease is one that “meet a prevalence threshold of not more than five affected persons per 10 000” (recital 55 PMD).

¹³² OJ 2006 C 146/1. This document is also referenced in the PMD (recital 22), as follows: “Systematic and continuous efforts should be made to ensure that quality and safety standards are improved in line with the Council Conclusions and taking into account advances in international medical science and generally recognised good medical practices as well as taking into account new health technologies”.

¹³³ *Ibid*, no emphases added.

operating principles, where quality of care is defined as follows:¹³⁴ “All EU health systems strive to provide good quality care. This is achieved in particular through the obligation to continuous **training** of healthcare staff based on clearly defined **national standards** and ensuring that staff have access to advice about **best practice** in quality, stimulating **innovation** and spreading good practice, developing systems to ensure good clinical governance, and through **monitoring** quality in the health system. An important part of this agenda also relates to the principle of **safety**.”¹³⁵

This aspect of quality of **training** of future health professionals and quality of care has also been emphasized by the ECJ in a Belgian case concerning access to higher education. In this case, the Court has stated as follows. “In that regard, it cannot be ruled out a priori that a reduction in the quality of training of future health professionals may ultimately impair the quality of care provided in the territory concerned, since the quality of the medical or paramedical service within a given area depends on the competence of the health professionals who carry out their activity there”.¹³⁶

In conclusion, while quality of care is, basically, to be defined at national level, there are some implications of EU law in this context. In case of cross-border healthcare, this task falls to the MST, not the MSA. The latter can of course refuse prior-authorization (both in general, as well as in an individual situation) in case of quality and safety concerns. EU law always refers to a high-quality treatment and the ECJ to the international “state-of-the-art”, in case one MS would argue that a certain treatment should be considered experimental, whereas another MS would see it as ‘normal’.

6 Conclusions and outlook

Health care systems across Europe still rely on national rules for their governance and service delivery and they also seem to be rather **closed** to external influences with some exceptions for border regions collaboration. The reason for this closure is related to the fact that health care finance as well as health care organisation are quite **different** across Europe (Thomson, Foubister, and Mossialos 2009) and it is often difficult to integrate them. Systems relying on some form of social insurance and an organisation that has implemented some form of quasi market (Jones and

¹³⁴ Ibid.

¹³⁵ Ibid, emphases added. Patient safety, which is closely linked to quality, has been defined as follows: “Patients can expect each EU health system to secure a systematic approach to ensuring patient safety, including monitoring risk factors and adequate, training for health professionals, and protection against misleading advertising of health products and treatments”; *ibid.* See also Frischhut, (2017), pp. 66-69.

¹³⁶ Case C-73/08 *Bressol* ECLI:EU:C:2010:181, para 67.

Cullis 1996) seem to be more **flexible** to accommodate for patient's mobility as one might expect. The purchaser reimburses health care, has to keep its budget balanced, but is not involved in health care supply planning. The purchaser is used to contract with providers and a price system is already in place for setting the cost of treatments. When prices across different health care systems are quite similar and providers are private entities, dealing with border patients' mobility may be simpler. In a more vertically integrated system or in the presence of mixed market that in Europe are still quite important (Levaggi and Levaggi 2020; Eurostat 2017), the purchaser has to keep demand under more strict control to match it with the local supply and with budget at central level. Hence, they may be more reluctant to allow patients to choose to be treated abroad.

Price differences are also quite important, especially after the enlargement of the EU. However, **after** the Covid-19 outbreak, there does seem to be **more** scope for **regulation** by the EU and intervention also in the health care market. Since the beginning of the Covid-19 pandemic, the European Parliament has conducted three Eurobarometer surveys dealing with the health topic: the special Eurobarometer survey "Future of Europe" in autumn 2021, the standard semi-annual Eurobarometer survey in spring 2021, and the flash Eurobarometer survey "Attitudes on vaccination against Covid-19" in May 2021 (this latter on a more specific topic).

The common theme is that the **trust** in EU seems to increase while the one in national government is slightly falling (Buso et al. 2023). In this scenario, the EU will have to find a **new role** as concerns health care. During the pandemic, it has acted as central provider for vaccines (Pircher 2022) and it certainly contributes to innovation through specific funding for rare and non-communicable diseases (Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety 2023b; 2023a). Although health care is a national competence and some recent studies have shown that for most functions national governments are the best choice (CIFREL 2020; Buso et al. 2023), the EU may still play an important role to **improve** both **efficiency and equity**. The Covid-19 crisis has also shown the value of **resilience**¹³⁷ for health care systems (Font, Levaggi, and Turati 2020), and to foster innovation.

A **recent study** commissioned by the EU (EU Commission 2022) has found mixed results on the achievements and shortcomings in the **implementation** of the **PMD**. The PMD has brought certainty and a clear legal framework for EU citizens to exercise their rights to cross-border healthcare, but, although it has removed some obstacles, still some important barriers to cross-border care persist. This has meant that the impact of the PMD has been minor for national health systems, but also

¹³⁷ Cf. also WP 2 within the Flash project.

has limited the benefits for patients in general. Furthermore, important differences exist at national level. For example, Nordeng and Veggeland (2020) compare Germany with Norway and show that the implementation is quite different: in Norway, a centralised system is used, while in Germany it is often the case that almost each sickness fund has its own reimbursement rules, so that the actual implementation of the PMD is rather different.

One of the open issues in this context is the role of **patients' mobility** in this scenario. In this report, we have tried to draw a picture as broad as possible of patients' mobility in Europe. It is however important to note that very little is known about actual patient's mobility flows across Europe, in spite of several attempts to get a clear picture. Several countries do not report **data**, some of those that respond to questionnaire are not able to distinguish between different types of mobility (European Court of Auditors 2019; Olsson, Smedt, and Wispelaere 2023; Olsson, De Smedth Lynn, and De Wispelaere Fredric 2021). This is certainly something that should be redressed as quickly as possible in order to get consistent data across time and countries. At present patients' mobility is a **marginal** phenomenon in Europe. Although numbers are not precise, its extent is about half the number of patients that move across the regions in Italy (Fondazione GIMBE 2023). However, patient's mobility has **potentials** that should be used to improve **equity and efficiency** across Europe. The present system may however need to be reformed and regulated. The **starting point** is to understand what drives mobility, which are the benefits that can be gained and which are the hurdles to overcome in order to get a **more flexible, effective and resilient** system.

Patient mobility across countries may be a driver for **equity** and **efficiency** at European level at least in the following four¹³⁸ different areas:

1. Treatment of **rare diseases**, which requires sunk investments in specific technologies: In this case, **coordination** at EU level would allow treating more rare diseases. While at national level the development and the maintenance of an excellence centre to treat patients may not be cost effective (the sunk cost for the investment may be higher than the benefits), the use of the technology at **EU level** may allow sharing the costs and redressing the cost effective (C/E) ratio. Coordination at this level could also mean that more rare diseases can be treated since some countries may specialise in some of them. Furthermore, countries with less technology/resources may benefit from their use, especially if the centres are **financed** at EU level and each country may send their patients to be treated free of charge or at marginal cost. In this respect, the PMD had foreseen some initiatives to improve treatment. As mentioned above, the PMD has

¹³⁸ The fifth area will focus on some legal questions.

defined a rare disease as any ailment affecting less than five individuals in 10000 (recital 55). There are about 6 to 8 thousand rare diseases and about 27 to 36 million EU citizens that have such ailments. The PMD has provided the framework for setting up **EU reference networks** with the aim to improve diagnosis and treatment (Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety 2023b). At present, there are 952 health care providers (mostly hospitals and labs) providers across Europe, but the **budget** rules have not been set in a convincing manner and such mobility may require additional financial resources (European Court of Auditors 2019). Furthermore, with the advent of **personalised medicine** and the use of sophisticated technologies such as CAR-T¹³⁹, the number of rare diseases may be increasing and it may be even more important than in the past to create a network across Europe to treat these patients. At present, the strategy is to finance providers, but it may well be that **other strategies** may prove to be more effective. For example, it may be worth to investigate whether to **finance** this **mobility** with the same mechanisms that may be envisaged for excess capacity (see below). In this context, we think that the principle of **solidarity** may be quite important so that differential prices may also be foreseen for patients moving from countries with a different income level.

At present, the existence of this expanding network of providers is certainly reducing one of the barriers to patient mobility, namely available information. The PMD had in fact foreseen the presence of national contact point that should have helped patients in finding treatments abroad. Most countries do not still comply with this requirement, and patients have to find information on their own (European Court of Auditors 2019). This of course creates a further hurdle to move and may represent a higher barrier for people with a lower level of health literacy. In this respect, the presence of the network allows to partially overcome this problem: it may be the local provider/GP/specialist that refers the patient to a centre abroad.

2. A better a more coordinated use of **excess capacity**: In the past few decades, the number of **hospital beds** has been drastically reduced in most western countries in order to improve **efficiency**. The reduction has however not been so uniform across Europe. In 2018 Germany was the nation with the highest bed per capita in 2018 (eight beds per 1,000), followed by Bulgaria and Austria. Most European countries have between three and seven hospital beds per 1,000 population, but numbers are lower in Sweden, Denmark, Iceland and the United Kingdom (OECD 2020). However, this reduction means that if demand increases for some fluctuations or some unexpected reasons, the health care system goes immediately under stress.

¹³⁹ See above note 95.

Likewise, in this case the Covid-19 pandemic has shown effects of bed shortages across Europe: apart from a higher **mortality rate**, when bed occupancy increased above a specific threshold, it was necessary to **lockdown the economy** to stop the contagion growth (OECD 2020; Lupu and Tiganasu 2022). For these events and (more effectively) when the increase in the demand occurs in a subset of countries, **planning** bed excess capacity **at EU level** may be beneficial for all the countries. The number of unused beds decreases, while the availability in case of need may increase. This type of patient mobility, a **two-part payment system** could be envisaged. While it is clear that Member States might be reluctant, the EU budget could pay the fixed cost for up to a specific number of beds in each country, while the running costs (when the beds are actually used) would be settled through a country agreement based on a cross-national tariff. In this case, each country could decide whether to invest in extra capacity or pay for using excess beds. This system has of course some legal aspects that need to be identified and solved: for example, if because of exceptional circumstances (as partially in the case of the Covid-19 pandemic) both countries need to access the spare capacity, which patients should use the beds first?

- 3. Improving quality through patient mobility:** From a theoretical point of view, the welfare effects of patient mobility across regions are not clear-cut (Levaggi and Levaggi 2014). Brekke et al. (2014) show that cross-border patient mobility may be beneficial for both patients from high and low skill regions, as in the classical model of international trade (Heckscher et al. 1991). Patients from high skill regions receive benefits from high skill hospitals, while patients in the low skill regions that value quality may receive their preferred level in the other region. However, patient mobility may have **countervailing** effects on welfare, when regions with a different level of income compete (Brekke et al. 2016). In the long run, theoretical model predict that quality-driven mobility should disappear: competition should provide a strong incentive to stimulate quality improvements in the less efficient jurisdictions (Brekke et al. 2012a), although evidence on this is still rather mixed (Siciliani and Straume 2019). In some countries, such as Italy, mobility seems to have created the opposite effect (Berta, Martini, and Albini 2018; Balia, Brau, and Moro 2020; Balia, Brau, and Marrocu 2017; Berta, Guerriero, and Levaggi 2021). The example of **Italy** is quite interesting, because apart from some border mobility that depends on budget issues,¹⁴⁰

¹⁴⁰ Each Region has a budget for health care for patients that are resident in the same region, while for cross border mobility there is not a threshold. This means that when waiting time depends on budget restrictions rather than supply shortage, patients can simply avoid the queue by receiving treatment in a neighbour region.

the long-distance mobility is from low income to high-income regions, something that may replicate the eastern/western flow in Europe. This mobility is still quite marginal at present and there should be a **debate** on its role at European level. Countries are reluctant to allow their patients to go abroad because of possible double costs: from one side they have to plan supply to allow everybody to be treated, but if some citizens decide to be treated abroad, there is going to be excess, unused capacity and extra costs due to the reimbursement for treatment abroad. Even if the PMD states that the **cost** for the national health care system should not be higher than what paid to patients within the country, the health care bill may increase. Furthermore, some countries use **waiting lists** as instruments to reduce health care expenditure growth. In this case, mobility can be used to reduce waiting time, but it is going to increase health care costs. In this respect, Italy is a good example of a system that is producing more damages than benefits. (Berta, Guerriero, and Levaggi 2021) analyse incoming patients' flows for Lombardy and shows that border mobility is often driven by waiting times: patients are usually younger¹⁴¹ and less severe than residents are, while for those coming from non-border regions hospitals ask for a higher reimbursement in spite of the same quality level and a Prospective Payment System (PPS). This implies that **resources flow** from poor to rich regions; **quality gaps** are deemed to increase and only patients that can move are allowed to get a better quality. In the light of these evidences, it may be important to carefully study, how mobility could be regulated and (co)financed at EU level. At European level, something similar seems to happen for the mobility from eastern to western countries. (Stan, Erne, and Gannon 2020) show that patients moving to other countries increase the equity gap across national individuals and they also find specific differences between native and migrants. Mobility increases the cost of health care hence increasing the quality gap. Again, at regional level (Amuedo-Dorantes, Rivera-Garrido, and Vall Castelló 2022) present the results of a policy implemented by Regions in 2012, in order to reduce mobility. The reduction does not seem to have affected equity in health care provision, but the study does not include long run effects.

4. Telemedicine¹⁴²

With the advent of **e-health** technologies for some diseases, the patient will be able to receive the state-of-the-art care in her own country, without the need to move. This may be done by sharing protocols among hospitals and health care centres. An interesting development is the establishment of

¹⁴¹ Concerning the elderly, cf. also WP 7 within the Flash project.

¹⁴² On the legal aspects of eHealth and telemedicine, see above Chapter 2.2, at note 75.

virtual consultation panels through the Clinical Patient Management System (**CPMS**), a dedicated IT platform and telemedicine tool developed by the Commission to allow healthcare providers from all over the EU to work together virtually to diagnose and treat patients. At present, these virtual consultations are underused and several administrative problems have to be solved, since in some cases they are not reimbursed. However, if they keep growing and become popular, their use may have to be coordinated across countries and waiting lists may arise. In this context, become important how the lists are formed in order to have an equitable system across EU partners.

5. From a **legal perspective**, one way of achieving a more **solidarity**-based approach would be to revise the existing cross-border healthcare regime. Without going into details, redesigning the cross-border healthcare acquis more from a community-based, not only from an individual patient perspective would strengthen solidarity in this field. Apart from amendments to existing rules, most patients do not know about the difference between the SSCR and the PMD.¹⁴³ **Merging** the directive into the regulation would reduce complexity, allow for a general (solidarity-based) revision, and thereby might **reduce injustice** related to knowledge (epistemic injustice in a broad sense).

¹⁴³ Hence, the statement according to which “cross-border healthcare ensur[es] clarity for Union citizens about their rights and entitlements” (PMD, recital 9) can clearly be further enhanced.

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Annex 1 – Heterogeneity in outcome and health care delivery across EU countries

Health care outcomes and delivery is quite heterogeneous across the EU Member States. For health outcomes, we can consider an aggregate indicator such as life expectancy and healthy life years. The variance across Europe is quite important.

Source: Eurostat (2023)
Figure 2 - Healthy Life Years, 2019

Healthy life years¹⁴⁴ vary from 53.1 years in Latvia to 73.3 in Sweden, with a rather important geographical variation between western and eastern countries in Europe.

A similar pattern emerges for **life expectancy**. In 2018, it was 81 years in the EU-27, but while Spain had the highest life expectancy (about 83 years), for other countries (Bulgaria, Latvia, Romania) it decreases to 75 years (OECD/European Union 2020). The gap is certainly due to a marked difference in lifestyle and incidence of non-communicable disease, but it certainly also depends on a different level of health care expenditure and efficiency across EU countries.

¹⁴⁴ The indicator healthy life years (HLY) at birth measures the number of years that a person at birth is still expected to live in a healthy condition. HLY is a health expectancy indicator, which combines information on mortality and morbidity. The indicator is also called disability-free life expectancy (DFLE). See (Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety 2015).

As per **expenditure**, Figure 3 shows per capita health care expenditure, PPP (purchasing power parity) adjusted in order to consider the cost differential across countries.

Source Eurostat (2023)

Figure 3 - Health care expenditure per capita, PPP adjusted for 2019 and 2020

Health care **expenditure** per capita varies significantly: while the EU average is around € 3.144 (Eurostat 2023), in some countries such as Germany and Norway it is about 3.76 times higher than in countries such as Bulgaria, Romania or Croatia. The Covid-19 crisis had increased expenditure, but it does not seem to have changed the gap. The same pattern can be observed for medical **equipment and technology** (CIFREL 2020).

Likewise, **efficiency** is quite heterogeneous across Europe both as concerns the production of **outputs** (i.e. the number of treatments provided to the population, both as concerns hospital admissions, specialist visit, diagnostic test, preventive care) and outcomes (increase in life expectancy or some health-related measure such as healthy life years or disability free life years¹⁴⁵). (Buso et al. 2023) show that there are countries that are efficient in producing outputs (i.e., Austria, Germany), but not outcomes, as well as countries very efficient in terms of outcomes (i.e., Italy,

¹⁴⁵ See (Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety 2015).

Spain), but not in terms of outputs, but again there is a difference on average between eastern and western countries in Europe.

A higher need combined with a lower expenditure may allow explaining the huge difference in **unmet needs**¹⁴⁶ across European Countries, as shown in Figure 4.

Source: Eurostat (2023)

Figure 4 - Unmet needs arising from barriers to access (cost, travel and waiting time)

¹⁴⁶ Unmet needs are a person’s own assessment of whether he or she needed examination or treatment for a specific type of health care, but did not have it or did not seek for it. EU-SILC collects data on two types of health care services: medical care and dental care.